

D1.7 Initial methodology for co-designing (local) Citizen Actions in CS Initiatives and Living Labs and Fab Labs

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Executive summary

This report introduces the more4nature methodology for co-designing Citizen and Community-Led Actions (CCLA) with civil society stakeholders, in collaboration with Living Labs and Fab Labs.

In the context of more4nature, Citizen and Community-Led Actions are interventions driven by individuals or groups aiming to protect the environment. more4nature is based on a broad understanding of the potential role of civil society actors in Environmental Compliance Assurance (ECA), explicitly including both citizen-generated data and Citizen and Community-Led Actions, both of which play a pivotal role to address issues and challenges with Environmental Compliance Assurance. This document situates Citizen and Community-Led Actions in the more4nature context of Environmental Compliance Assurance, and outlines the initial methodology aimed at supporting civil society actors in their co-design of CCLAs.

Part I of this document explores which and how different civil society actions relate or contribute to collaborative ECA, using the more4nature framework for analysis of the case situation (Wehn and Pfeiffer, D3.1 Methodology for double Loop Action Research 2024). This report introduces six aspects of particular importance for situating and characterizing CCLA contributions to collaborative ECA Specifically,

1. Identifying **actor groups** involved in CCLA(s) in an ECA-related context;
2. Understanding CCLAs as **targeted interventions** of civil society actors aiming to change behaviour of other actors (CCLA targets);
3. Establishing the **purpose of CCLAs** based on the reasons for non-compliant behaviour in the case situation;
4. Clarifying how CCLAs **create and affect relationships** and interaction patterns between civil society actors, duty holders and institutional actors;
5. Distinguishing key **CCLA action resources** from the ECA action resources of state actors;
6. Linking the **potential outcomes of CCLAs** to intended outcomes of the more4nature case learning journeys.

These aspects build a solid conceptual frame, which can be used as the basis for the elaboration of the guidance to civil society actors as part of the co-design methodology. The document also assembles a collection of types of actions that are available to civil society actors as an action resource, in line with the more4nature conceptual framework. A total of 9 types of CCLA are elaborated and documented from the perspective of how citizens and communities can act within each, outlining potential targets, purposes and contributions to intended outcomes.

Part II of this document provides the practical reference for the co-design process, by describing a series of co-design cards that address the above-mentioned aspects. These co-design cards are complemented with case-based inspiration in the form of *Action Pathways*, that help illustrate the variety of paths civil society actors can take in their CCLA co-design and implementation process. Finally, special attention is given to

promote interactions with other initiatives, networks, in particular Living Labs and Fab Labs, to support the CCLA co-design and implementation process.

This methodology will be used in the Action Research activities of the 20 Pioneer cases, and it will be made available in an adapted format to civil society stakeholders in relevant more4nature Pioneer and Follower cases, in order to support their CCLA co-design activities. For that purpose, this document is intended as a reference for the implementation of the co-design methodology, which takes place in the context of Task 3.5 (T3.5). Selected content of the present deliverable will be made available to relevant more4nature partners (i.e. Pioneer case contacts), and who will use it with case stakeholders in the CCLA co-design process as part of case activities.

The final version of the more4nature CCLA co-design methodology (D1.8) with refined guidance materials will be produced by month 46 (October, 2027), based on feedback and inputs from more4nature cases, obtained during the double loop Action Research.

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Glossary of terms

Term	Definition
Action Resource	Action resources” refers to all tangible and intangible assets that create capacity and space for actors in the case situation to exercise their agency.
Action Pathways Repertoire	Collection of inspiration and living knowledge about the diversity of possible paths to take toward the co-design and co-production of CCLA in the context of ECA. This repertoire not only showcases real-world examples from a variety of contexts, but presents them from an implementation perspective, so that users easily reflect on their own possibilities and resources.
Citizen & Community-led Action	Actions and interventions for improving the implementation of environmental rules on the ground, related to the three pillars of ECA, taken or initiated by individual citizens, civil society organizations or communities.
Citizen Generated Data	Data streams generated through Citizen Science.
Citizen Science	Citizen science (CS) refers to the involvement of civilian actors in various forms of collaborative data and knowledge generation, including science-driven projects, initiatives to democratize science and policy via science citizenship, civic and community-based (environmental) monitoring, and citizen observatories.
Citizen Observatory	A particular form of CS that provides the means for new forms of interactions between policy-makers, the general public and the scientific community. CO involve ICT-facilitated bi- and multidirectional data and information flows, typically linked to participatory processes in environmental monitoring and governance.
Co-design Methodology	Methodology for more4nature pioneers to support civilian actors in taking actions in the context of ECA, composed by general guidance, inspirations of CCLAs via <i>Action Pathways and</i> practical tools for CCLAs along with other resources.
Collaborative environmental compliance assurance	Citizens and communities - in partnership with relevant authorities - collaborate in promoting, monitoring and acting to protect the environment.
Compliance	Act of submitting or yielding power to an authority and doing what is expected or required under a rule system enacted by that authority.
Compliance Promotion	range of actions that authorities undertake to help businesses and individuals meet their obligations, and to prevent or reduce infringements and the harm that they cause.
Duty-Holders	Natural or legal persons, including public authorities, who must respect obligations derived from EU environment legislation when carrying out activities that involve emissions into or other physical impacts on the environment.
Environmental Compliance Assurance	“All the ways in which public authorities promote, monitor and enforce compliance with the relevant rules” (European Commission).
Environmental Compliance Monitoring	All forms of inspection, surveillance and investigation undertaken by Environmental authorities to verify compliance or discover and characterise infringements.

Term	Definition
Environmental enforcement	Actions drawing on administrative, criminal and civil law to stop, deter, sanction and obtain redress for non-compliant conduct and encourage compliance.
Environmental litigation	Court cases on environmental issues involving citizens, companies and/or governmental and non-governmental actors.
Fab Labs	Fabrication Laboratory. A small-scale workshop offering open access to (personal) digital fabrication, which can be used by the public to create transform creative ideas into tangible prototypes.
Learning Journey	Facilitated 5-stage process stimulating social learning among stakeholders of the more4nature Pioneer Cases.
Living Lab	mechanism developed to support innovation by offering a 'neutral arena' where different stakeholders would be able to meet and co-develop innovative solutions.
Social Learning	Intentional process of collective sense-making and knowledge co-creation with the aims of boosting cooperation and learning among multiple stakeholders.
Social Protest	Strategic forms of action designed to influence decision making, either directly or by influencing public opinion via the use of the media and the internet.
Typology of actions	Type of actions defined by more4nature partners to involve citizens and communities in the context of environmental compliance.

Table of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CCLA	Citizen and Community-Led Actions
CFM	Community Forest Management
CGD	Citizen Generated Data
CS	Citizen Science
ECA	Environmental Compliance Assurance
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
ICT	Information Communication Technologies
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization

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1 Introduction

1.1 more4nature project summary: Vision, objectives and project organization

The more4nature project endeavours to catalyse transformative change in conservation efforts regarding zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention, by strengthening the role of citizens and communities in environmental compliance assurance (ECA) via Citizen Science (CS), Citizen Generated Data (CGD), and Citizen and Community-Led Action (CCLA). The overall vision is supported by five specific objectives. The project will:

1. Define an **overarching conceptual framework for collaborative environmental compliance assurance**, building on systemic behavioural and relational models that detect obstacles and opportunities for involvement of civil society actors in compliance promotion, monitoring and enforcement. Action research in 20 Pioneer +20 Follower Cases will explore and test a set of behavioural best practices and technical tools derived from the framework and promote their adoption via the project knowledge platform and other dissemination means.
2. Develop Trusted and FAIR principles for data governance, data validation and data management, to **qualify its citizen-generate data for the European Green Deal Data Space (GDDS)**. The project will adopt the necessary building blocks as defined by the Data Space Support Center and the Great project and opt-in as a node in the GDDS, to enable the sharing, community validation and reuse of citizen-generated data and information as complement to official observations.
3. Generate indicators using the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), **establishing CS as one methodology for elaborating policy indicators in compliance monitoring**. Including CGD-based indicators in the shared Scientific Data Space creates exposure, enables comparative analysis with legal thresholds, and supports the generation of temporal tendencies and future projections in an integrated way for the benefit of local/regional/nations authorities.
4. Empower citizens and communities, creating and exploring spaces in which **civil society actors play an active and accepted role in collaborative ECA**. The objective is to move beyond general collection of high quality CGD, towards targeted contribution of complementary and accepted data to formal compliance monitoring indicators and systems, support for compliance promotion and compliance enforcement through community-led actions co-designed with competent authorities, and contributions to policy design and policy evaluation.

5. **Transform current ECA practices of authorities and enforcement agencies**, enabling the combination of official data and citizen science data to improve reporting on implementation and progress within formal monitoring frameworks. CS is increasingly accepted as a source of reliable data, but a deeper transformation is needed to enable meaningful collaboration between authorities and civil society actors in ECA mechanisms and integrate CGD in the monitoring frameworks for zero pollution, biodiversity protection and deforestation prevention.

To achieve its objectives, the more4nature project works with a large number of existing CS initiatives which are interested in increasing and institutionalizing contributions to ECA. To stimulate transformative change in current ECA practice, the project will assist these cases with a process of social learning and socio-technical experimentation, combined with provision of algorithms, models, and interoperable systems to public authorities, to encourage the intended validation and uptake of citizen observations for ECA.

1.2 Background

The more4nature concept of *collaborative Environmental Compliance Assurance* (ECA, Figure 1) provided in deliverable D3.1 - *Methodology for Double Loop Action Research* (Wehn and Pfeiffer 2024) stipulates how civil society actors can contribute to the three pillars of formal ECA (compliance promotion, compliance monitoring and compliance enforcement), as well as to the environmental policy cycle.

Figure 1 more4nature concept of collaborative Environmental Compliance Assurance (source: more4nature consortium)

more4nature is based on a broad understanding of the potential role of civil society actors in ECA, explicitly including contributions both through:

- Citizen Generated Data (CGD) - data generated by diverse forms of CS initiatives.
- Citizen and Community-Led Action (CCLA) - actions and interventions, taken or initiated by individual citizens, civil society organizations or communities.

In the context of more4nature, Citizen and Community-Led Actions (CCLAs) are interventions driven by individuals or groups aiming to protect the environment. They include a wide variety of possible activities, ranging from volunteers monitoring or restoring sites, to publicity campaigns, to protests and boycotts, to civil lawsuits (more detailed discussion see *Situating CCLAs in the more4nature conceptual framework*). Regardless the form of those activities, “taking action” has a relational and emotional impact on the individuals and/or communities initiating or taking part. When the CCLA stems from a collective effort, actions both depend on and strengthen internal relationships of the group, as shared experiences during actions can transform groups into communities or even social movements (Porta 2008). CCLAs can have a positive impact on the individual and can create long-term benefits that go beyond the impact of the desired ends: create shared beliefs, solidarity and knowledge acquisition (Tarrow 1994). At the same time, CCLAs often touch on complex ethical and legal issues as civil society actors assume responsibility for public policy and position themselves in specific roles towards institutional or other private stakeholders (see more4nature deliverable D6.1 and *Actor groups involved in CCLA(s) in an ECA-related context*). In some instances, “taking action” related to ECA can create risks to personal safety, including opposition or prosecution from state actors. In other words, taking action can produce effects and have consequences not only on the system (authorities, corporations or public opinion), but also on the people that are part of those actions (Porta 2008). These effects can take more extreme forms of violence and repression, as documented by international NGO Global Witness¹, or the Environmental Justice Atlas². Further, relationships and emotions involved are dynamic and situations can escalate in unintended and unanticipated ways. Therefore, facilitating the co-design of CCLAs in the context of ECA in more4nature requires special attention. This includes both the need for a deep understanding of possible actions civil society actors can take and how they might contribute to ECA, as well as a dedicated co-design methodology with detailed guidance to civil society actors, that also, first and foremost, is designed to keep people safe.

1.3 Purpose of the document

This report is produced by T1.5 to present:

¹ Global Witness Website: <https://www.globalwitness.org/>

² Environmental Justice Atlas: <https://ejatlas.org/>

1. The project’s approach for situating CCLAs in the context of collaborative ECA in general, and for developing specific Action Pathways in relevant more4nature cases.
2. A typology of actions with the potential to empower citizens and communities and create spaces in which society actors play an active role in Environmental Compliance Assurance.
3. the more4nature methodology for co-designing Citizen and Community-Led Actions with civil society stakeholders, in collaboration with Living Labs and Fab Labs.

The CCLA co-design methodology hereby presented will be used by relevant more4nature cases as integral part of the overall Double-Loop Action Research activities that guides the Learning Journeys of relevant 20 Pioneer and 20 Follower cases (Wehn and Pfeiffer, D3.1 - Methodology for Double Loop Action Research 2024). This initial version of the CCLA co-design methodology is intended as a reference document for the more4nature partners who will make it available to case stakeholders in their work with the more4nature Pioneer Cases. The final version of the more4nature CCLA co-design methodology (D1.8) with refined guidance materials will be produced by month 46, based on feedback and inputs obtained during both cycles of the more4nature Action Research.

1.4 Structure of the document

This document is structured in two parts.

Part 1 focuses on clarifying the notion of civil society actors “taking action” as part of an effort to strengthen ECA. It describes the approach followed for producing this deliverable, including a review of related literature (chapter 1), to define, situate CCLAs in the context of more4nature (chapter 2), and develop a typology of CCLAs relevant to collaborative ECA as envisioned by the more4nature project.

Part 2 focuses on the people intending to deliver Citizen and Community-Led Action(s) as contribution to collaborative ECA. It introduces the more4nature CCLA co-design methodology, with three distinct chapters that are aimed to: **guide** the CCLA co-design process (chapter 1), **inspire** CCLAs via *Action Pathways* (chapter 2) and **promote interactions** with Living Labs and Fab labs (chapter 3).

Part I Conceptualizing individual and civil society action as part of collaborative ECA

1 Review of existing academic and experiential approaches to structuring CCLAs

This chapter describes the approach followed for producing this deliverable. First, we describe the literature review process (section 1.1) which supports the production of this document in the following aspects:

1. **Characterise and refine** our understanding of Citizen and Community-Led Actions (CCLAs), via literature review, drawing concepts and inspiration from various domains, such as social movement literature, environmental justice, among others (see Characterizing CCLAs).
2. **Situate** CCLAs in the context of Environmental Compliance Assurance (ECA) (see *Source*: the authors
3. Defining CCLA in the context of environmental compliance assurance).
4. **Understand CCLA examples** by means of case-based literature review, to identify which factors shape CCLAs in different contexts, and what are the conditions for success (see *Understanding CCLA examples*).

Additionally, to leverage the experience of more4nature partners, a workshop was designed as part of the face-to-face interactions in the second more4nature consortium meeting in Copenhagen (28 - 30 May 2024). The result of this workshop helped inform the literature review in general, and to provide examples for the case-based literature (see section 1.2).

Finally, to better inform how the co-design of CCLAs may benefit from establishing synergies between CS initiatives and other initiatives, organisations and networks, such as Living Labs and Fab Labs, section 1.3 is dedicated to explaining the process followed to understand how these synergies may be established.

The literature review, combined with collaborative research with more4nature partners and the ecosystem of Fab Labs and Living Labs has contributed to shape the results presented in part II, helping in the conceptualisation of the different type of CCLAs as well as the elaboration of a customised guidance. In particular, the elaboration of this guidance is informed by the above-mentioned inputs with the identification of key aspects to address in the overall approach for the co-design methodology, as well as in the interactions with Living Labs and Fab Labs and providing sources for *inspiration* to the cases.

1.1 Literature review

As outlined above, a literature review aimed at better understanding and building a common set of references regarding the concept of Citizen and Community-Led Actions (CCLAs) for collaborative Environmental Compliance Assurance (ECA) was conducted. Additionally, case-based literature was reviewed to build upon the current understanding of CCLAs in both academic and grey literature, and to identify

conditions, variants and approaches to CCLA from different fields. A total of 272 references were identified and analysed (see **Error! Reference source not found.**).

The literature review was carried out in two steps. First, core questions and keywords were identified to define CCLA in a broader context, therefore bringing knowledge from various domains, including but not limited to citizen science and community-led practices regarding environmental protection (see Table 1). In a second step, the focus was narrowed to consolidate the typology of actions identified in the context of collaborative ECA in more4nature deliverable D3.1, by defining and identifying keywords and adding a series of references for each CCLA type. The complete list of keywords is outlined in Table 3.

This process helped to find case-based and comparative analysis literature on the different CCLA typologies and to collect specific guidance that can serve the more4nature cases in their CCLA co-design work.

1.1.1 Characterizing CCLAs

To delineate the spectrum of CCLAs, the first step of the literature review consisted of gathering articles from various domains to better situate and define CCLAs in the context of environmental protection in a broad sense, reflecting the diversity of Citizen and Community-Led Actions.

Table 1 summarizes key **domains** and their **contributions** to help define several aspects of CCLAs, from environmental justice to advocacy and social resilience.

Table 1 Domain contributions to CCLAs

Domain	Contributions to defining CCLAs
Environmental Science and Ecology	Provides methods for data collection, monitoring, and conservation, enabling communities to contribute to scientific research.
Social and Environmental Justice	Focuses on addressing environmental inequalities, ensuring marginalized communities have a voice in environmental policies.
Community Development and Urban Planning	Supports sustainable development and resilience, offering frameworks for collaborative design and participatory urban management.

Domain	Contributions to defining CCLAs
Public Health and Environmental Health	Emphasizes the links between environment and health, guiding community actions that aim to reduce health risks from pollution.
Education and Environmental Literacy	Builds ecological awareness and encourages sustainable behaviours, fostering a knowledgeable and engaged community.
Policy Studies and Governance	Informs advocacy efforts, helping communities understand and influence policies that affect local environmental management.
Psychology and Behavioural Science	Explores motivations for participation and enhances community cohesion, supporting long-term volunteerism and stewardship.
Sociology and Anthropology	Offers insights into community values and social structures, integrating Indigenous and traditional knowledge into environmental practices.

Source: the authors

In addition to the above domain contributions, the characterisation of CCLAs can be informed by existing approaches and processes, spanning from co-creation processes, environmental justice and social movements, grassroots communities, environmental stewardship and resources management, conservation and restoration projects, activism and cultural initiatives (see Table 2). The approaches can be compared according to their core objectives and expected impacts, the typology of stakeholders and their engagement strategy, as well as on the structure of the action process.

Table 2 Inspirational approaches of CCLAs in environmental protection

	Description	Main CCLA Stakeholders	Main process & key activities	Examples
Co-creation & Design (Eckhardt, y otros 2021) (Liedtke, y otros 2012)	Collaborative Design of sustainable solutions addressing environmental challenges, tailored to community needs	Quadruple Helix	Explore, Engage, Ideate, Prototype, Test and Reflect	Living Labs, Innovations from materials, products, services, systems, policies, Regenerative practices

	Description	Main CCLA Stakeholders	Main process & key activities	Examples
Environmental Justice Initiatives and Research (Davies and Mah 2020) (Raphael and Matsuoka 2024)	Communities, especially those disproportionately affected by environmental harm, mobilize to demand accountability, justice, and policy reform	Affected Indigenous Peoples, communities, NGOs and environmental defence agencies	Raising awareness, documenting issues, advocating for change, decision-making Community-based participatory research	Protests against polluting industries, campaigns for clean water access, and advocacy for reduced air pollution in marginalized areas. Indigenous Peoples and local community actions to stop illegal deforestation
Environmental Stewardship and Natural Resource Management (Fabricius y Collins 2007) (Obeng-Odoom 2021) (Stephen R. Kellert 2000)	Responsible use, protection, and conservation of natural resources for the benefit of current and future generations	Indigenous Peoples Conservation institutions, Local Residents, Managing authorities	Engage, Learn, Plan, Adapt, Sustain, Advocate	Indigenous Peoples lands and territories Community forests, watershed management initiatives, community-driven wildlife conservation efforts.
Conservation & Restoration projects (Armitage, et al. 2020) (McKinley, y otros 2017)	Restoring ecosystems and conserving natural habitats.	Indigenous Peoples, Associations, Landowners, Volunteer, Knowledge holders	Learn, plan, conduct, monitor, adjust, Engage with	Wetland restoration, creating wildlife corridors, and building rain gardens.
Advocacy and policy design (Armstrong 2024)	Engaging actions to foster policy changes at the local, national or international levels	Public Agents, Civil Society Organisations, Grassroots Activists, Local Residents	Situate, Gather, Build Consensus, Design, Advocate, Adopt, Assess	International Campaigns, Community petitions, town hall meetings
Artivism and Cultural Initiatives (Curtis, Reid and Reeve 2014) (Rodriguez-Labajos 2022)	Raising awareness and inspiring actions on environmental issues.	Artists and Creators, Activists and Community Organizers, General Public	Explore, Connect, Create, Develop, Attract, Share, Evaluate	Exhibitions, Performances, Murals, Eco-theatre, Community art projects.

Source: the authors

1.1.2 Defining CCLA in the context of environmental compliance assurance

To better situate these broader definitions of CCLA, and to selectively draw knowledge from the above-mentioned fields when appropriate, T1.5 was involved in the in-person and online discussions that led to the identification of different CCLA typologies in the context of T3.1, that later on was consolidated in D3.1. That selection is used as a basis for the typology outlined in Part I, chapter 3 of this document. Due to the project timing, this process was conducted in parallel, and several iterations were done with task participants as the work of both, T1.5 and T3.1, progressed.

To consolidate those initial results and better inform the literature review process, T1.5 partners requested inputs from more4nature project partners to work on defining each type of CCLA with a short text definition, a list of examples and associated keywords. In Table 3, an overview of the keywords and collected cases is presented.

The inputs collected in this table served as a starting point for further literature review of both concepts and cases, selection that is further complemented and improved over time by contributions and additional review of sources.

Table 3 Keywords and main references for each CCLA type

CCLA type (from D3.1)	Keywords for Literature review	References
Volunteer contribution	Environmental Volunteering Duty Holder volunteer engagement	(García-Valiñas, Macintyre y Torgler 2012) (West, Dyke and Pateman 2021) (Wong, y otros 2021) (Yumagulova, y otros 2021)
Take solution-driven practical action	Co-creation – Design Environmental/Eco/Sustainable/Circular Innovation Nature-based Solutions Living Labs	(Eckhardt, y otros 2021) (Mega 2019) (Carrillo-Hermosilla, del Río y Könnölä 2010) (Cuomo 2022) (Hadfield, et al. 2024) (Huss y Enevold 2023) (Liedtke, y otros 2012) (Struck, et al. 2022) (Zavratnik, Superina and Stojmenova Duh 2019) (Örtl 2022)
Reward compliance of duty holders	Community Champions Ecosystem Services Environmental Bonus & Incentives Environmental Certifications Environmental Awards	(Lindsay, et al. 2019) (Reid, Huq and Murray 2010) (Loos, et al. 2023) (Pietta and Tononi 2021) (Segerson 2022) (Derchi, Davila y Oyon 2023) (Segerson 2022) (Gatti, y otros 2022) (Minkov, et al. 2020)
Engage duty holders to encourage compliance to target	Prevention Education & Awareness Consulting	(Rogers 2022) (Sandra, Suriyati and Rasyid 2023) (Dubois 2024) (Pénzesné Kónya, Haigh and Křeček 2021) (Hoang, et al. 2021) (Kanda, y otros 2018) (Klewitz, Zeyen y Hansen 2012) (Sovacool y Dunlap 2022) (Stapper, Van der Veen and Janssen-Jansen 2020)

CCLA type (from D3.1)	Keywords for Literature review	References
		(Beveridge 2019) (Neal, Neal and Brutzman 2022)
Engage with media to generate attention about the topic/policy	Public Engagement Media Advocacy Climate Activism Environmental Communication	(Breen, et al. 2019) (Armstrong 2024) (Khatibi, et al. 2021) (Kumpu 2022) (Dahlan 1994) (Hansen 2018) (Priest 2022)
(Radical) activist action to promote compliance	Environmental Activism Local and global activism Environmental social movements Environmental Justice	(Apostolopoulou, et al. 2022) (Armiero, Rosa and Turhan 2024) (Fritsvold 2009) (Ganglbauer, Reitberger and Fitzpatrick 2013) (Jacqmarcq 2021) (Kirsop-Taylor, Russel and Jensen 2023) (Mihaylov and Perkins 2015) (Milstein, McGaurr and Lester 2021) (Saunders 2013) (Scheidel, et al. 2020) (Raphael and Matsuoka 2024) (A. R. Davies 2020)
Create additional detractors /citizen watch - guardians	Citizen observatories Patrols Environmental detractors	(Hager, Ajates, y otros 2021) (Hager, Gold, y otros 2021) (Woods, y otros 2021) (Austen 2015) (Wehn, Bilbao, y otros 2021)
Drive for change to admit CGD for reporting	Civic Monitoring Community-based Monitoring	(Berti Suman, Balestrini, y otros 2023)
Drive for change in targets / monitoring like inclusion of CDGs	Civic Monitoring Theory of Change	
Advertise acts that can be committed with impunity	Environmental Impunity Negligence Environmental Whistleblowing	(Miliband, Affairs and Group n.d.) (Cedillo and Clercq 2021) (Cody 2024) (Coelho-Junior, y otros 2022) (Leclerc 2024) (Zoppoli 2024)
Engage authority to enforce target	Environmental court cases, Nature Rights	(Bodansky and Asselt 2024) (Komoliddin 2024) (Lamara n.d.)
Take legal actions or request authority to do so		
Radical activist action inhibits noncompliance by duty-holders	Non-violent actions Environmental activism Resistance	(Sovacool y Dunlap 2022) (Berglund and Schmidt 2020)

Source: the authors

1.1.3 Understanding CCLA examples

An additional source for the literature review was the selection of various review articles (total of 12 articles) in the field of environmental conflicts research, environmental justice and environmentally focused social movements analysis. This review was conducted to provide an understanding of the underlying factors and the different approaches that enable environmental defenders to take action as a basis for providing actionable guidance to the more4nature case stakeholders. This is particularly relevant for the more4nature CCLA co-design methodology, as it provides guidance on what strategies have higher chances of success, based on previous experience. The review was done with a wider purpose, and included various references from the above mentioned fields, including, but not limited to, work on the [Environmental Justice Atlas](#) (Scheidel, et al. 2020) with worldwide references of various fields, and other cases with a narrower geographical focus (Hess and Satcher 2019), or thematic focus such, for instance on mining conflicts (Aydin, et al. 2017).

1.2 Experience-based knowledge of more4nature project partners

In addition to the literature review, an in-person workshop was held in the 2nd more4nature face-to-face meeting, held in Copenhagen (28 - 30 May 2024). During this workshop, more4nature partners participated in a collective exercise that helped gain insights into their collective experience in the field of CCLA. The activity was facilitated by IAAC and used the online MIRO platform as support for better capturing information directly in a digital format. During the session, more4nature partners worked in groups, with at least one case lead in each group, and filled a template of past CCLA actions that they were involved in, or had knowledge of, in the past. Figure 2 shows two pioneer case contacts summarizing the results of the activity. At a later stage, this material was used to create a table with cases, and link those to the CCLA typologies that were being defined in the context of Task 3.1. This exercise served two purposes: 1) engage the more4nature partners with the CCLA concepts, creating a common understanding of Task 1.5 and the task partners themselves in order to 2) identify examples that could be used in the case-based literature review. Table A 1, in Annex I, shows the result of this data collection.

Figure 2 Citizen & community-led actions in collaborative ECA according to more4nature partners during the F2F workshop in Copenhagen, May 2024

1.3 Networking for CCLAs: Living Labs and Fab Labs

To support the co-design of CCLAs for environmental protection, synergies and connections are promoted to join forces between CS initiatives and other initiatives, organisations and networks. These synergies are encouraged to implement, or even co-design, such actions from scratch, and they may entail establishing connections with Living Labs, including those from EU Missions, as well as artists, placemakers and makerspaces communities and networks, such as Fab Labs. Further details on each one of these initiatives and networks, how these connections may be established, and what are the potential gains are described in Part II, chapter 3. The case of artists and creatives is covered as part of the *CitiObs Citizen-led action toolkit* (Guy y Gonzalez 2023). In this section, we describe the approach followed to better understand how to establish connections with Living Labs and Fab Labs.

A review was conducted to gain a better understanding on how **Living Labs** can be approached as part of more4nature’s co-design of CCLA activities, and in particular, to better grasp the current status of EU Mission Living Labs. First, existing inventories of Living Labs (ENoLL), including their (Tricarico, et al. 2023), to gain insights into the scope and capabilities of ENoLL members. Next, relevant projects from the EU Missions calls were identified, such as FarClimate³, OSS Energy⁴, PrepSoil⁵, and , and [SOILL2030](#), to explore their goals and contributions to environmental protection on soil health and climate action. Finally, an online discussion was conducted with ENoLL representatives to identify opportunities for collaboration, addressing key

³ FarClimate Website: <https://farclimate-project.eu/>
⁴ OSS Energy website: <https://www.oss-energy-community.eu/>
⁵ PrepSoil Project website: <https://prepsoil.eu/>

questions such as how Living Labs can support CCLAs, ways to find relevant Living Labs, their current activities related to ECA, and potential opportunities for collaboration with specific more4nature pioneer cases. SOILL2030⁶, to explore their goals and contributions to environmental protection on soil health and climate action. Finally, an online discussion was conducted with ENoLL representatives to identify opportunities for collaboration, addressing key questions such as how Living Labs can support CCLAs, ways to find relevant Living Labs, their current activities related to ECA, and potential opportunities for collaboration with specific more4nature pioneer cases.

In the case of **Fab Labs**, given the connection of Fab Lab Barcelona (part of the Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia, IAAC) to the global Fab Lab Network, a different approach was followed. The Fab Lab Network gathers yearly on a global event of Fab Labs, that took place in Puebla, Mexico in August 2024. As part of the conference, IAAC submitted a proposal to the open research paper stream to develop an analysis of the Fab Lab Network regarding their involvement in environmental protection activities, which aimed to understand how Fab Labs have connected with environmental protection activities that seemingly do not pertain to their core activities (i.e. open fabrication laboratories where users can use, and learn how to use, digital fabrication techniques). Within this analysis, a short desk research, and a series of semi-structured interviews with 10 Fab Labs from different continents (Europe, Africa, and South America) was conducted (González, Calvo Juarez and Guy 2024). This effort provided a better understanding on how Fab Labs have developed relationships with existing local or foreign environmental initiatives, how those relationships have evolved, and presents key insights for the recommendations the more4nature case stakeholders willing to engage with them.

⁶ SOILL2030 website: <https://www.soill2030.eu/>

2 Situating CCLAs in the more4nature conceptual framework

In this chapter, we situate the CCLA concepts outlined above within the context of the more4nature project work, exploring which and how different civil society actions relate or contribute to collaborative ECA. The basis for the elaboration is the more4nature framework for analysis of the case situation (Wehn and Pfeiffer 2024) (Figure 3), which identifies the core actor groups involved in collaborative ECA, frames the action resources of institutional and civil society actors, and conceptualizes core behavioural dynamics.

Figure 3 more4nature conceptual framework (Wehn and Pfeiffer, 2024)

For the purpose of this deliverable, six aspects are of particular importance for situating and characterizing CCLA contributions to collaborative ECA. Specifically,

- Identifying **actor groups** involved in CCLA(s) in an ECA-related context;
- Understanding CCLAs as **targeted interventions** of civil society actors aiming to change behaviour of other actors (CCLA targets);
- Establishing the **purpose of CCLAs** based on the reasons for non-compliant behaviour in the case situation;
- Clarifying how CCLAs **create and affect relationships** and interaction patterns between civil society actors, duty holders and institutional actors;
- Distinguishing key **CCLA action resources** from the ECA action resources of state actors;

- Linking the **potential outcomes of CCLAs** to intended outcomes of the more4nature case learning journeys.

2.1 Actor groups involved in CCLA(s) in an ECA-related context

CCLAs are driven by, and targeted at, actors in the more4nature case situation. Therefore, both the typology of ECA-related CCLAs, and the CCLA co-design methodology need to be based on an understanding of the potential actors involved in the process, as participants, collaborators and as targets of interventions. The more4nature conceptual framework, elaborated in D3.1, identifies as relevant groups institutional actors and civil society actors on the one hand, and duty holders on the other hand (compiled from (Wehn and Pfeiffer 2024):

i) Institutional actors are authorities with a formal role in ECA, including

- **Environmental regulators, inspectorates and other authorities** involved in implementing environmental regulation, for example by operating permit systems, monitoring and reporting on compliance levels, and enforcing regulation through administrative tools;
- **Enforcement agencies** involved in response to (criminal) non-compliance, including police officers, rangers, or customs agencies;
- **Actors of the legal system** involved in corrective actions, including prosecutors and judges; and
- **Legislative bodies at all levels**, from local councils to national parliaments, who are charged with the oversight of authorities and enforcement agencies and have legal rights to question and influence how formal laws are translated into agency-internal policies, strategies, and priorities.

ii) Civil society actors

- **CS initiatives** focused on biodiversity, deforestation, or pollution reduction/prevention, that produce Citizen Generated Data (CGD) and with an interest in expanding their activities into compliance assurance.
- **Citizen and community-led initiatives interested in taking actions** to strengthen compliance assurance for biodiversity protection, pollution or deforestation reduction/prevention, for example through outreach and engagement of relevant actors, public education, direct supportive actions such as volunteer habitat clean-ups, interception of illegal logging, or legal cases.

iii) *Duty holders*

The third group of relevant actors emerges from environmental regulation itself. It encompasses all **natural and legal persons, including public authorities, who are expected to comply** with obligations derived from binding legislation or non-binding agreements when carrying out activities that impact the natural environment⁷.

Industries and companies are the most important group of duty-holders in environmental regulation. Economic activities with substantive environmental impacts including extractive industries, agriculture, or manufacturing, are typically restricted to registered and licensed entities. Duties are sector-specific, but typically include:

- Obligations to obtain permits for the extraction, use and trade of resources,
- obligations to obtain permits for the use, recycling, emission, or disposal of pollutants,
- obligations to design production sites and processes in specific ways to reduce the risk of environmental degradation and disasters,
- obligations to document, monitor and report operational details to environmental authorities; as well as
- obligation to grant authorities access to commercial operations for purposes of monitoring and inspection.

While many regulated economic activities are commercial and profit-oriented, the core regulated entities are not necessarily private businesses. At global scale, large segments of extractive industries and utilities are state-owned, and large state actors such as the military are both subject to environmental regulation and hold commercial interests in many countries. The resulting intrinsic conflict of interest will be further discussed in section 2.2.3.

Private individuals form a second group of duty-holders under environmental regulation. While they are excluded from regulated economic activities listed above, they are targeted in other roles, for example:

⁷ more4nature uses the term “duty holder” in line with European legal terminology, referring to natural and legal persons with duties and obligations to comply under a law (see EUR-lex, EC 2018). Note that this term must be distinguished from the nomenclature of rights-based approaches, which is similar but with inverse meaning. Rights-based approaches define as “duty bearers” public officials with duties and obligations to enforce the rights awarded to “rights holders” by laws. Duty-bearers as understood by rights-based approaches are “Institutional ECA actors” as listed under (i).

- As land owners, with duties to limit uses of private land to permitted activities;
- as owners of buildings, vehicles and consumer goods, for example regulating permitted levels of emissions or disposal of expired goods;
- as users or visitors of public spaces such as forests, lakes or nature reserves, including restrictions of access and imposition of direct behavioural rules (no littering, no open fire, no cutting of trees etc.).

A third group of relevant duty holders is created by international law, in particular in the European Union (see more4nature deliverable D1.1). The legal framework of the European Union creates duties for *member states* to transpose, implement, and report on environmental regulation created at the European level. And while not legally binding, international conventions assign responsibilities and create behavioural expectations that can be the basis for collaborative ECA actions in line with the more4nature approach.

Duty holders differ across the 40 more4nature case studies, and have to be identified case by case, as each case is focused on improving compliance with different rules, laws, or regulations, and each rule set imposes duties and obligations to a different set of duty holders.

To identify relevant duty holders for a case, the project will use the term ‘duty-holder’ in a broad sense. It is applied both to actors with formal duties under binding legislation, and to actors merely encouraged to accept responsibilities in laws or by non-binding international agreements. However, for the co-design of CCLAs it is not sufficient to identify duty holders. The rationale for actions is created by the way duty-holders respond to regulation, specifically whether duty holders are *compliant* or *non-compliant*.

2.2 CCLAs as targeted response behaviour

2.2.1 Defining CCLAs as intentional behaviour

As defined above, Citizen and Community-Led Actions (CCLAs) are **interventions driven by individuals or groups aiming to protect the environment by influencing the behaviour of persons, companies or organisations with an impact on the environment**. The concept of CCLA shows parallels with those of *social protest*, defined as “strategic forms of action designed to influence decision making, either directly or by influencing public opinion via the use of the media and the internet” (Hanna, et al. 2016, 219). In this context, *decision making* is referred to as “any process for the conceptualisation and implementation of planned interventions at any level, in both corporate and political settings” (Hanna, et al. 2016, 219).

Conceiving CCLAs as a means for civil society actors to influence the behaviour of others entails the recognition that the ‘action’ in CCLA itself also is a behaviour, i.e. of civil society actors. Following (Ajzen 1991), in line with the more4nature conceptual framework, intentional behaviours can be defined in terms of

- their **target**, i.e. directed at specific persons, companies, or institutional actors;
- the **activities** involved to realize the intention (supportive via provision of knowledge or resources; or critical by exerting pressure);
- the **context** in which actions they occur, in particular in terms of interactions with the targets and other actors;
- the **time frame** over which the activities are carried out (date(s) and length).

This definition is in line with the understanding of CCLA based on social movement literature (see section 1), where different forms of action are defined as “social movement repertoire” (Della Porta 2010) with actions taking different forms and serving different purposes, organized as individual actions or in “campaigns” or “clusters of actions”, but always “embedded in a socio-political context and each society has different norms and accepted ways of (taking action)” (McAdam, Tarrow and Tilly 2001).

2.2.2 CCLA targets

The targets of a CCLAs are the persons, companies or other institutions whose behaviour or decisions the intervention aims to influence. As elaborated in the more4nature conceptual framework, ECA-related actions are ultimately responses to the behaviour of non-compliant duty-holders. Citizens often directly derive the sense that there is need for action from seeing the presence and impact of non-compliers in the case area, i.e. their own local environment. This includes, for example,

- living in a heavily polluted or degraded environment, especially where emission of pollutants or other negative impacts of economic actions is observable;
- observations that corporate actors benefit from activities that degrade the environment, while citizens experience impacts on their health and wellbeing;
- observations of actors breaking rules or engaging in illegal activities such as logging or poaching that lead to environmental degradation with impunity.

In such cases, actors responsible for environmental degradation might be chosen as **direct targets of CCLAs**. In many cases, the targeted behaviour will represent non-compliance with existing environmental regulation. However, this is not a necessary condition for civil society action. Corporate or individual conduct might be legal, but still perceived as unjust based on moral norms.

Non-compliant duty-holders can originate not just from individual or private sector backgrounds, but also from institutions. Institutional stakeholders participating in the more4nature case area are frequently duty-holders with responsibilities in the implementation of environmental regulation themselves, and might be chosen as targets of direct CCLAs as well. Again, the double role of public authorities as duty holders and ECA actors can lead to conflict of interest, and civil society actors taking actions against them creates complex challenges (see section 2.2.3).

However, institutional actors can be targets of CCLAs not just in their role as non-compliant duty-holders. Civil society actors might hold public authorities responsible for the compliance situation, for example:

- Perceiving issues with the transposition of international agreements into national legislation or failure to create plans, strategies and instruments that make existing legislation enforceable (institutional actors targeted in their role as legislators or decision makers);
- Perceiving a lack of efforts in promoting, monitoring and enforcing existing regulation towards duty holders (institutional actors targeted in their role as ECA actors);
- Perceiving that regulation is implemented in selective, unjust or unethical ways, with issues ranging from structural bias to conflicts of interest and outright corruption (institutional actors targeted based on the conduct of public officials in the execution of their office).

Addressing such perceived issues changes the context for actors that have negative impacts on the environment. Accordingly, public authorities can be chosen targets of CCLAs as an **indirect way of influencing non-compliant duty-holders**. For the CCLA co-design methodology, it is crucial to understand why the current compliant situation is happening, in order to identify both direct targets and indirect targets whose behaviour influences the observed issue.

2.2.3 CCLA activities and their purpose in an ECA context

The social movement *repertoire of actions* represents “a limited set of routines that are learned, shared and acted out through a relatively deliberate process of choice”. In the context of social movement analysis, (Hanna, et al. 2016) suggest seven purposes for *protest* events (which we relate to some CCLA types in this context): information, fundraising, publicity, mobilization, solidarity building, political pressure and direct action (see reference for definitions). And informed by the literature review (section 1), the typology presented in section 3 describes nine **types of actions** widely practiced. The more4nature co-design methodology, in particular the *Action pathways* outlined in Part II, provide guidance for cases that consider implementing such CCLAs as part of the case Learning Journey.

However, the generic typology of actions appears to be ambiguous in the context of ECA, and insufficient to make relevant choices during the co-design process. The ambiguity is created by the indicated nature of CCLAs as behaviours responding to the behaviour of other actors, with a range of direct and indirect targets. An action such as “generating public pressure” requires further definition to clarify who is the target of the public pressure and what purpose the public pressure is supposed to achieve. To position CCLA activities in the more4nature conceptual frame, and to clarify their potential role in the context of collaborative ECA, is helpful to once more consider the definition of CCLAs as intentional behaviours responding to the behaviour of non-compliant duty holders. Non-compliance can take many forms, as duty-holders accept

or reject obligations and responsibilities for a range of different reasons. Current best practice in formal ECA already links tools of the three ECA pillars (compliance promotion, monitoring, enforcement) to types of duty-holder behaviours (see Figure 4). The approach proposes that reasons for non-compliance range from lack of knowledge or resources needed to comply with regulation, to contemptuous, opportunistic or criminal disregard for rules. Proposed ECA responses measures are matched to the underlying causes of the compliance situation.

Figure 4 Types of behaviours of duty-holders to regulation and matching ECA interventions

Source: (European Commission 2017)

CCLAs might be considered the equivalent of policy instruments of civil society, and the choice of actions follows a similar logic. Specifically, this logic implies that civil society actors initiating CCLAs should clarify the purpose of their actions based on an understanding of the reason for the behaviour of their chosen, direct or indirect target. The types of behaviours represented in the approach above by and large divide non-compliant duty holders into two groups: On the one hand are duty holders who are likely to change their behaviour if they had additional information, resources, or a stronger sense of urgency. On the other hand are duty holders who will most likely remain non-compliers until they are pushed, deterred or prosecuted. Following this logic, CCLAs in the context of ECA serve one of two fundamental purposes. They either support or enable targets who are generally willing to comply and will potentially change behaviour if provided with additional resources, knowledge or an enabling environmental push and generate pressure on targets who are generally unwilling to

change. It should be noted that most types of actions presented in chapter 3 can serve both purposes. Defining a CCLA in terms of its purpose involves deciding HOW a specific type of action will be done.

Supportive CCLAs

CCLAs directed **towards targets who are confused, careless, and or under-resourced** serve to change behaviour by altering the knowledge and resources available to them. Supportive actions take place to achieve **improvements within the boundaries of the existing institutional system**.

Civil society actors can provide assistance to duty holders directly, and fostering compliance promotion is to provide incentives, in both positive and negative approaches. Further strategies using incentives can be concrete benefits to duty holders when they comply or voluntarily report non-compliance, including recognition programs, financial incentives, or even public pressure (OECD 2009). Financial incentives fall out of scope for the types of CCLAs that are available in the context of the more4nature case stakeholders. However, other incentives may apply, that link to public pressure (both in positive and negative forms), and that can be seen as rewards and motivation or means to deter non-compliance. In addition, “positive” strategies can include promotion of “environmentally friendly” duty holders, although their practical effect seems to be limited (at least at government level).

It should be noted that the more4nature vision of collaborative ECA is based on the idea that engagement of civil society actors can strengthen the environmental compliance assurance system as a whole, with citizens adding capacities, skills and resources to the formal ECA efforts. This implies a natural space for CCLAs that target institutional non-compliers with supportive action.

Critical CCLAs

CCLAs directed towards targets who are opportunistic, contemptuous or criminal serve to influence behaviours and decisions of targets by generating social and institutional pressures. The term ‘critical’ has been chosen to reflect of the principles of critical theory, which includes questioning, challenging and improving the institutional system itself.

When targeting non-compliant duty holders directly, CCLAs can exert pressure by using different strategies, that can leverage similar approaches to those found in *Generate public pressure*, *Denounce violations that are committed with impunity*, or *Inhibit non-compliance via civilian interventions*. This includes actions that are aimed at influencing the policy formation cycle, primarily driving for the acceptance of citizen generated data in official environmental reporting schemes, or as part of the monitoring frameworks and policy targets. CCLA types available for these purposes involve advocacy and lobbying strategies, formal requests and recommendations, and frequently require expert knowledge of the legal framework, of the monitoring

schemes in place, and of when the windows of opportunity are available (for instance, when there is a new directive being drafted).

“Official” mechanisms that allow CCLAs to exert pressure on government agencies are done via complaints or in court, in order to enforce regulatory requirements. Citizens have different options available to them depending on the country where they are located. For instance, direct access to courts is possible for civil society actors in some countries like Finland only if they are direct victims of a violation, while in other cases, they must complain to environmental authorities. In the Netherlands, citizens can petition the authorities to enforce environmental requirements and file a case in administrative court if they fail to do so (OECD 2009). This reflects the complexity of the enforcement system in each country, and how interactions with legal experts and NGOs may be necessary in each case. Additional pressure can be exerted by other means, for instance through direct mailings to authorities, or contacting environmental law enforcement.

In addition, although public pressure can be an effective strategy, it is closely related to access to environmental information and the understanding of legal limits. Depending on the context, **communities can leverage partnerships** with environmental NGOs or human rights CSOs, experienced networks or the media to gain further access and knowledge on these instances in case of need, as knowledge co-production (i.e. the combination of knowledge from both, communities and experts or experience networks) plays a fundamental role in strengthening the capacity and the collective sense of identity (Herrero and Vilella 2018). The specific type of organisations and partnerships to be pursued will need to be assessed on a per-case basis, accounting for how citizens and communities perceive trust in relationships and the history of those in the past.

2.2.4 CCLA context and interactions with targets and authorities

The literature review highlighted the relevance of the context in planning CCLAs, and both the more4nature double loop Action Research methodology and the CCLA co-design methodology contain comprehensive tools for analysis of the case context (see (Wehn and Pfeiffer 2024), Part II). For the purpose of situating CCLAs in in more4nature conceptual frame, a key aspect is created by the interactive nature of civil society action. For one, with their chosen actions, civil society actors publicly document a normative judgement regarding the behaviour and decisions of the target actor(s). Furthermore, civil society actions are initiated by self-motivated volunteers, but are introduced into an existing ecosystem of public actors interacting with duty holders based on legal mandates. CCLAs thus add new interaction patterns to the case situation. And while civil society actors are free to choose action targets, action types and the main purpose of the action, but they are not able to control how targets and other actors in the CCLA ecosystem will respond to their initiative. Accordingly, the co-design of CCLA actions has to consider the attitude and existing relationship between relevant actor groups, and decide which interaction approach is realistic and fit for purpose. Specifically, interactions can be collaborative or confrontational.

- **Collaborative interactions** engage actors in spaces with limited social pressure, share and involve sharing information, consultation, the discussion of shared goals and mutual contributions towards such goals
- **Confrontational interactions** engage other actors in public spaces exposed to scrutiny and social pressure, and focus on progress towards goals unilaterally set by the civil society actors.

Again, the interactions approach has no clear relationship to the type of action or purpose of the action, and can be different for different actor groups in the ecosystem. For example, civil society actors can choose a confrontational approach to interactions with private sector duty holders as targets, for example by deploying guardians, denouncing violations, or through civil law suits, while coordinating the actions with environmental authorities (collaborative approach to interaction). Furthermore, it is important to appreciate the difference between critical CCLAs and a confrontational approach to interactions. As example, reporting non-compliance to authorities is a critical action that aims to push contemptuous non-compliers into changing their behaviour. However, if observations are conducted discreetly, and reporting is done using protected channels, civil society actors will not have to confront the non-compliant target in the process. This similarly applies to actions that advocate systemic improvements to ECA practice. For example, regulators frequently face challenges created by badly drafted legislation with vague or enforceable targets or lacking means if implementation. In such cases, public officials might welcome a highly publicized civil lawsuit that exposes legal issues and exerts pressure on legislators to fix policy gaps.

At first glance, such detailed definition of interactions might appear overly complicated. However, they are of crucial importance, especially for cases that involve

- Powerful duty-holders with high monetary stakes. Such actors cannot be confronted without exposing civilians involved to significant risks
- Public authorities with conflicts of interest as both duty holders and ECA actors. If such actors are unwilling to change, a confrontational approach might be the only action option, with civilians facing repercussions from authorities and enforcement agencies.
- ECA actors benefitting from non-compliers through corruption. Depending on the context, civil society actors may be exposed to prosecution, threats, or even physical violence from public authorities.

The fact that ECA actors themselves might be non-compliers and the risks to personal safety involved in civilian action create two crucial implications for the CCLA co-design process:

First, the process needs to include extensive consideration of plans from an ethical perspective (see deliverable D6.1). Cases have to clarify which behaviours of duty holders and ECA actors are ethically desirable and which are legal under the written text, ensure that issues are addressed at the right level (policy or implementation), but and refrain from supportive actions and collaborative interactions with if legal

provisions or related ECA practice is recognized as bias or unethical. Bias in the implementation and enforcement of regulation arises from the way the common general norms are interpreted, specified, balanced and negotiated in their application. For example, individuals or groups monitoring the enforcement of environmental regulations may feel emboldened to “gatekeep” in the name of environmental enforcement, and consciously or otherwise, allow biases to influence who is targeted for enforcement. This may result in discrimination and reinforce discriminatory and oppressive power structures, a concern that is particularly relevant in cases with indigenous populations as duty-holders of environmental regulation.

Second, the more4nature vision for collaborative ECA implies that CCLAs should not fundamentally undermine the possibility for collaboration between civil society and public actors. Possible civil society actions identified in the literature include forms of protest and radical activism that would place civil society actors in direct conflict with public authorities to a degree that would make subsequent collaborative actions difficult or impossible (e.g. protest involving violence, sabotage and property destruction). Such actions are forms of CCLA, but they would not contribute to ECA, and as such should not be supported or implemented as part of more4nature project activities.

2.2.5 CCLA timeframe and temporal dynamics

For all CCLAs, it is important to consider the temporal dimension, as actions and responses to such action evolve and change over time. People (individuals or communities) may engage in and/or initiate CCLAs to trigger a response, generally from duty holders, responsible authorities, policy makers or private businesses. However, the response to the CCLA may materialize in different ways, and it may not address the concerns that drove people to take action. It is common that situations escalate when responses are not addressing those concerns (Bjørst 2016) and, for that reason, mechanisms are needed to measure CCLA outcomes, and facilitate iterations, seeking other forms of action, or different channels to create influence when necessary.

Building on the dynamic and iterative nature of CCLA, actions may not be limited to a single event, but “short actions” may be part of a “campaign”. In other instances, actions may take place over long periods of time and will gain richness and complexity as those relationships evolve (González, Calvo Juarez and Guy 2024). Diversity in the approaches, as well as careful consideration of the timing of the actions, has proven to generate impact in those cases where environmental injustice is more prominent (Scheidel, et al. 2020). Similarly, when different forms and functions are combined, especially when deploying digital forms of protest, CCLAs are more likely to be successful and achieve success (Bjørst 2016).

2.3 CCLA action resources

In the more4nature project, the term “Action resources” refers to all tangible and intangible assets that create capacity and space for actors in the case situation to exercise their agency. Three aspects are particularly relevant for the CCLA typology and co-design methodology.

1. The importance of social relations and emotions as source of agency, allowing civil society actors to take action without legal mandates and with limited resources.
2. The types of action resources needed for effective CCLA and created through CCLAs.
3. The complex ethical and practical challenges created by the difference in action resources of different actor groups.

A distinct and specific characteristic of CCLAs is the importance of emotion, as well as the sense of community and solidarity in social collectives as a primary action resource of civil society actors. Taking action has an emotional impact on the individuals that are part of the process, and it's motivated by their sense of responsibility towards perceived impacts on the environment. This is linked to the legal origin of compliance assurance, or, more specifically, to the fundamental difference between institutional (state) and civil society (non-state) actors in their responsibility for public policy. Specifically,

- **Citizens (or non-state actors)** have rights they are entitled to, but face restrictions that reflect both the rights of others, and submission of the individual to the authority of the state. While citizens have the right to express environmental concerns, they have no mandate or authority to impose obligation on each other. There is no such thing as civil ‘enforcement’ if it involves any form of physical force or coercion.
- **State actors** have the authority to interfere with the rights of non-state actors, but they do not have any natural rights themselves. All powers have to be mandated and enumerated in detail and are subject to restrictions in how powers are exercised, reflecting rights of citizens. Typically, every rule imposed by the state has to be justified (Grechenig and Kolmar 2011).

Institutional actors are provided with action resources through powers enumerated in legal mandates, operational guidelines and procedures, budgets, and the tools of the three ECA pillars. Civil society actors have action resources in the form of CS tools, CGD sets, as well as in resources such as media channels that can generate public pressure, or available options for civilian legal actions. However, the different nature of civilian and state action resources creates a substantive power imbalance, underlying many of the ethical challenges outlined in section 2.2.4. Analysis of action resources can be a useful to for addressing such challenges, and reduce the personal risks of individuals and groups implementing CCLAs. As example, the level of discretion given to institutional actors in applicable regulation determines opportunities for corruption and selective enforcement, an issue that could be targeted

at the policy level through improved distribution of powers, or introduction of check and balances.

For the purpose of co-designing CCLAs, a key aspect is that **tangible action resources alone are not sufficient to create civil society action. CCLAs require actors with strong motivations, as well as relevant skills and capacities.** This aspect is observable in the fact that formal platforms for public engagement in policy (tangible action resource) frequently remain underused. In many cases, civil society actors either lack the knowledge, skill, time or resources to engage with such platforms, or they refrain from engagement because they do not believe that engagement would lead to a result.

With regard to skills and knowledge, CCLAs can create spaces for dialogue, and opportunities for collective action networks in which cooperation with external actors can become beneficial. In this sense, networking “in action” can be instrumentally important for increasing the influence of each organisation and individual, as well as strengthening their capacities and skills. The collective experience in that they are “not alone”, and this process helps develop social ties (Porta 2008). This is conceptualized as “network environmentalism” (Johnson, y otros 2014), where community members collaborate with advocacy groups, policymakers, and researchers to promote environmental protection. In the context of the more4nature CCLA co-design methodology, beyond the CS initiatives engaged in the cases in more4nature, networking can be fostered with external like-minded organisations (or clusters of those) such as Living Labs (in particular those with environmental focus overlapping more4nature’s thematic areas) and Fab Labs, whose role in environmental initiatives as “enablers” was explored as part of the short-term study mentioned in the literature review (González, Calvo Juarez and Guy 2024). Note that **more4nature project activities will themselves generate new action resources for civil society actors.** Both individual citizens or communities are considered potential initiators and implementors of CCLAs, and project activities involve interacting with other organisations, initiatives, legal experts or networks to complement their expertise or join forces. Special attention is paid in more4nature to potential interactions with Living Labs, artists, placemakers and makerspaces, such as Fab Labs, that may support the co-design process of CCLA at various stages.

Maybe the most important action resource for CCLAs is intangible and intrinsic. Civil society action is driven by a sense in individuals that “something needs to be done”, situated in a personal and social context that identifies goals and chosen actions as legitimate and acceptable. Accordingly, CCLAs cannot be understood without consideration of social norms and concepts of justice in applicable belief systems. As civil society actors have no formal mandate for action, material resources, knowledge and skills have to be activated either by individual intrinsic motivation, or a situation enabling collective action. Furthermore, the process of “taking action” creates relational and emotional impact on the individuals and/or communities initiating or taking part in those CCLAs, which can substantially change the context for CCLAs over time. In a positive sense, joint actions can create positive

environmental impacts, strengthen internal relationships, turn loose groupings into communities. However, CCLAs can have a negative impact on individuals in various ways, impacting them directly in terms of personal safety, among other consequences, which needs to be carefully considered. more4nature aims to stimulate transformative change that makes collaboration of institutional and civil society actors in ECA a positive and rewarding experience. Whether this can be realised depends on the case context and how authorities will respond to CCLAs.

2.4 Contribution to intended more4nature case outcomes

The final aspect of situating CCLAs in the more4nature conceptual frame concerns the question of how CCLAs relate to the more4nature vision for collaborative ECA. The above sections defined actions relevant to the ECA context in general. However, there is no direct correlation between CCLAs and collaboration levels. In fact, civil society groups may deliberately choose *critical* and *confrontational* approaches, if such actions align with motivations and shared belief systems. Accordingly, defining the intended outcomes of intended actions in the co-design process establishes CCLAs as a specific contribution towards the transformational change envisioned by the project.

For the purpose of more4nature cases, changes in three areas are considered relevant as outcomes for a transition towards collaborative ECA under the project's conceptual framework. First, changes in compliance practice leading to increased levels of compliance; second, the form and level of collaboration and trust among core actors, and finally, changes in the state of the environmental resource (Wehn and Pfeiffer 2024).

2.4.1 Contributions to changed ECA practice and compliance levels

CCLAs might contribute to improved ECA practice and compliance levels through:

- Actions that **directly contribute to preventing non-compliance** of duty holders, meaning that civil society involvement leads to improved compliance promotion in the case context;
- Actions that **directly contribute to discovering and diagnosing non-compliance** by duty holders, meaning that civil society involvement leads to improved compliance monitoring in the case context;
- Actions that **directly improve the response to non-compliant behaviour** of duty holders, meaning that civil society involvement leads to improved enforcement in the case context;
- Actions **that strengthen the systemic capacity of institutional ECA actors** in the case context, meaning that civil society involvement contributes to improved formal ECA practice in indirect ways.

CCLAs contributing to **compliance promotion** present rich impact potential. Large scale actions to raise public awareness for environmental issues, or generate urgency

and social pressure to implement environmental regulation, are a typical strength of civil society action, whereas formal ECA actors rarely focus resources on social pressure mechanisms.

CCLA contributions to **compliance monitoring** include all **means suitable to verify compliance levels, detect and deter infringements**. For example, citizen guardians and environmental patrols can watch over the territory and detect and report offences. These reports can involve further involvement of competent authorities, and can enhance their capacity to detect, or be aware of, new forms of non-compliance that may not have been identified before.

CCLA contributions to **enforcement** includes as primary action types reporting of non-compliant behaviour to competent authorities to initiate formal enforcement action; and the legal actions in the form of civil lawsuits. In addition, the restoration of degraded environmental systems is becoming more relevant as corrective measure in the prosecution of non-compliant duty holders. In this regard, civil society actors might also play a role in overseeing or implementing restorative actions imposed as sanctions on non-compliers.

It should be noted that **environmental monitoring plays a cross-cutting role** in these contributions. Civic data collection and monitoring can take various forms and use various technologies, from inventorying natural resources at large scales, to reporting of perceptions (such as smells) and day-to-day observations as indicators of offenses. Both volunteer data collection activities and resulting knowledge and CGD can be linked to a variety of CCLAs. For example, the declining status of resources such as air, water or biodiversity is often difficult to monitor, and degradation is caused by numerous small and diffuse actions. While an overall decline of resources is visible and accepted in general terms, a sense of urgency needed for effective compliance monitoring is often lacking. Here, civil society can play a significant role, with Citizen Science initiatives augmenting available data, and CCLAs for both, to generate CGD, and to make results visible in meaningful ways to generate public pressure. Monitoring for the purpose of infringement detection also generates potential evidence for enforcement actions and, in doing so, contributes to deterring non-compliance.

CCLAs not only contribute to the specific ECA practices, but might **strengthen the systemic capacity of the ECA system** as a whole. Improvements can take place at the policy level with new or revised policies and the generation of new ECA action resources by policy makers, or from supportive CCLAs.

2.4.2 Contribution increased collaboration and trust

Sections 2.2.4 and 2.2.5 emphasize the interactive nature of CCLAs, with clear implications for the level of collaboration and trust in the case context. However, the direction of the impact is not linked to the type of action. **There is no type of action that, by default, would increase or undermine trust or collaboration**

among actors. *The relevant aspect is how civil society actors define their specific CCLA in the co-design process, specifically whether actions are designed*

- as supportive or critical actions; and
- as collaborative or confrontational in their interaction with institutional ECA actors in the case context.

In general, actions that chose a critical and confrontational stance towards public authorities involved in the situation are likely to have negative impact on collaboration levels, while actions designed to be supportive and collaborative in their interaction with ECA authorities have a higher potential to contribute to increased trust as outcome of the more4nature case Learning Journey. In extreme cases, it might be possible that very few confrontational actions might derail collaboration in the Learning Journey of the case as a whole. However, this should not lead to the conclusion that cases should generally prefer supportive and collaborative actions. Confrontational approaches can be highly effective, and CCLAs are often motivated by the desire to confront actors engaging in offensive behaviour. A crucial question for the co-design process is to analyse the CCLA ecosystem as a whole, identifying actors who should be pushed and confronted on the one hand, but also clarifying if there is space to collaborate with related authorities interested in the intended outcome at the same time.

For example, there are several ways trust/distrust can be channeled to different competent authorities, as a CS initiative could distrust local institutions, but trust others at higher (national, EU, UN) level. Being able to choose allies for CCLA, supporting actors in their networks, define targets and accommodate for potential iterations, are key factors to consider and facilitated as part of the CCLA co-design methodology both in the initial stage (see

CCLA Ecosystem Card in Part II section 1.1) as well as in the iterative approach that it follows.

2.4.3 Contribution to environmental outcomes

Finally, the urgency and enthusiasm for the community to act can be channelled through ameliorative measures, which can be an important mechanism that helps trigger a direct impact on the local environment. However, depending on the context, these strategies may be better linked to the above-mentioned assistive or incentive promotional strategies, or other strategies found in different sections, as they may be perceived as simplistic and only looking at short-term outcomes, or the limited involvement of the community on working towards more fundamental issues.

2.5 Implications for the CCLA Typology and Co-Design methodology

The more4nature CCLA co-design methodology focuses on the role of civil society actors (both individual citizens and groups or communities) and what they expect when being part of CCLA processes directed at addressing ECA issues.

The analysis has shown that there are numerous **types of CCLA** that can be implemented to address ECA issues, (see 198 different methods of nonviolent action in (Hanna, et al. 2016)). One difficulty in creating a CCLA typology is the observation that most types of actions have no clear relationship to *targets*, *goals* or even the *tone* of a planned intervention. As one example, demonstrations can be organised to support collaborating actors by raising public awareness and the profile of an issue, or they can aim to exert public pressure on institutional actors in highly confrontational ways. The type of actions (their form), that are available to (or applicable by) a community or an individual citizen highly depends on their social, political and cultural context and the ECA issue to be addressed. This context may change over time, as both the person's individual or the group's collective knowledge and relationships evolve, both within the community itself and with external actors and duty holders. Both these processes, and public opinion, media and social media iteratively influence each other and feed back into the different events and the strategies potentially available to CS initiatives.

However, this does not de-value the collection and documentation of existing practices. In the inventories cited above, civil society participants adopt “scripts they have performed or at least observed before” (McAdam, Tarrow and Tilly 2001, 138) (see section 2.1) and, according to this view, “it is uncommon to innovate an *efficient* new action”, but rather “rework known routines in response to current circumstances” (McAdam, Tarrow and Tilly 2001, 138). This builds upon the social processes detailed above, as well as on people's individual or the community's collective ability to embark on these processes (and to coordinate among themselves). Therefore, being able to learn from other (more experienced) communities, or be inspired by previous

experiences is a key opportunity that should be seized during the co-design of a CCLA. In line with the more4nature conceptual framework, the Typology of Actions presented in Chapter 3 can be considered an Action Resource for civil society actors.

Regarding implications for the CCLA co-design methodology, the above analysis shows that the overall Learning Journey of the relevant cases (as devised in D3.1 (Wehn and Pfeiffer 2024)), and the co-design process of specific CCLAs are closely interconnected and mutually influence each other. As such it is important to consider that all steps of the CCLA co-design process are embedded in the larger transformative change process towards collaborative ECA. To support the more4nature civil society stakeholders, the CCLA co-design methodology presented in this deliverable invites users to review collected examples in the form of *Action Pathways* (see section under the same name for reference), and to design and iterate their own CCLA. They are also invited to define the form and purpose of the CCLA, in the co-design methodology (see in

Deliverable D1.7

CCLA Goal Card section).

3 Typology of Actions

3.1 Overview

In this section, potential types of CCLA are elaborated and documented from the perspective of how citizens and communities can act within each, outlining potential targets, purposes and contributions to intended outcomes. In addition, for each form, a curated compilation of examples, tools and references is presented, aimed at enabling more4nature case stakeholders to gain insights and practical tools for each type of action and identify the resources they need to implement them, as well as references to specific examples in the *Action pathways* section.

Therefore, each CCLA type is elaborated with respect to the following:

- *Detailed description of the activity*
- *Potential targets of the action:* which behaviours and actors can be targeted with the action
- *Potential outcomes of the action:* indicate how the action might contribute to improve compliance assurance, policy, systemic capacity of the ECA system or the natural environment.
- *Examples:* List of case-studies identified as inspiration for each type of action, some of which are detailed in the *Action Pathways* section.
- *Selected tools:* List of tools that were identified as relevant for the type of actions. They are summarised in Annex II.
- *Additional resources:* List of articles, books and research papers that are recommended to read to go deeper in the definition of actions.

Table 4 Overview of CCLA types for ECA

CCLA short hand	Description	Potential targets (whose behaviour is to be influenced)
Assist duty holders to encourage compliance to target	Provide information, training and resources to duty holders about their legal obligations and best practices.	(Uninformed and under-resourced) duty holder(s), both compliant and non-compliant
Generate public pressure	Generate positive or negative incentives by generating pressure by the general public or a specific section of the population. Involves engaging with mass media, or selected channels and generating attention on a topic, or by using other rewarding mechanisms for compliant duty holders.	All potential targets of direct and indirect actions (duty holders, policy makers, public officials)

CCLA short hand	Description	Potential targets (whose behaviour is to be influenced)
Demand changes in environmental practices	Demand changes aligned with the "common good", including environmental concerns, via protest, advocacy, rallies. May involve NGOs, Environmental Movement Organizations	Duty holders, legislators, ECA actors
Proactive conservation and recovery actions	Physical activities to prevent, regenerate, restore or rewild.	General public (citizens as duty holder with collective responsibility for policy outcomes)
Citizen watch - guardians	Surveillance of non-compliance either via civic data monitoring or environmental patrols. This can contribute to triggering inspections, notifying authorities of non-compliant behaviour, or deterring non-compliant behaviour directly.	(opportunistic, contemptuous and criminal) non-compliant duty holders, environmental authorities, enforcement agencies
Denounce violations that are committed with impunity	Denounce illegal practices and/or non-compliant behaviours (social sanctions via naming & shaming). From journalism to art, including web campaigns to create public pressure on duty holders and/or enforcers.	(contemptuous and criminal) non-compliant duty holders, ECA actors targeted for their conduct
Report non-compliance to authorities	Engage with authorities to enforce legislation by reporting non-compliance.	(opportunistic, contemptuous and criminal) non-compliant duty holders
Take legal action	Sue duty holder or institutional actors and take legal action to hold them accountable for their environmental violation or inaction. Includes formal petitions to authorities to enforce legislation.	All potential targets of direct and indirect actions (duty holders, policy makers, public officials)
Inhibit non-compliance via civilian interventions	Blockage of duty holder activities, occupation of sites, boycott, from non-violent to violent actions.	(Contemptuous and criminal) non-compliant duty holders

Source: based on D3.1, (Wehn and Pfeiffer 2024)

3.2 Types of Action

3.2.1 Assist duty holders to encourage compliance to target

Definition

Provide information, training and resources to duty holders about their legal obligations and best practices.

How can this be done?

At a general level, this set of actions aims to **assist duty-holders in understanding and meeting their obligations** by, for instance, providing clear and accessible information on environmental laws and standards, coupled with training programs that build the knowledge and skills needed to meet these obligations effectively (Dubois 2024). These strategies may be more beneficial especially in cases where other compliance mechanisms (monitoring or enforcement) can't cover duty holders effectively, either because they are too numerous), or because there is a lack of knowledge or capacity to comply (confused or under-resourced duty holders), or because there is cultural resistance to enforcement (OECD 2009).

Different formats can be used to provide access to information on environmental knowledge, legal requirements, or obligations, both in formal and informal contexts. Both build upon previously acquired knowledge that the CS initiative or community may have generated from self-investigation, or as part of interactions with other experts and networks (Conde 2014). In both instances, this knowledge can be mobilised within the community, as they gain (self-)recognition as a legitimate source of expertise and information as they interact and potentially develop relationships with other communities and expert networks with shared interests or struggles (Herrero and Vilella 2018).

CCLAs can then be developed in both formal and informal educational and awareness-raising activities, equipping individuals and organizations with the knowledge on how to act or implement in environmentally compliant ways (Hoang, et al. 2021). Intermediaries play a vital role in providing or disseminating such information, acting as consultants, connectors and translators of complex legal or technical concepts to ensure duty holders fully understand and can apply best practices (Neal, Neal and Brutzman 2022) (Beveridge 2019). Citizens and communities can be active in such activities as knowledge providers or as initiators.

The way in which this form of CCLA is implemented depends on the complexity of the topic and the relationships of the initiating citizens and communities with duty holders and expert groups. When relationships are amicable, and the legitimacy of the CS initiative as a knowledge provider is not under scrutiny, it may take that role directly in both formal or informal settings, combining education and training, potentially along with (online) resources, and support networks to provide duty holders with

better knowledge of legal requirements. This approach can be considered as informative spaces and arenas for conversation with duty holders (OECD 2009). However, in non-amicable situations, especially if there is a high degree of technicality in the environmental degradation assessment (i.e. specific equipment is required), partnerships may be necessary with like-minded expert networks (such as toxicity experts, health experts, etc.) that may support this initiator role and help them gain recognition in their claims (Herrero and Vilella 2018). In this sense, this could be seen as “Activism mobilising science” (Conde 2014), where local knowledge and scientific knowledge are combined in new forms of “knowledge co-production”, gain better understanding on issues, and avoid entering in the framing of complex Environmental Impact Assessment or information exchanges, which tend to neutralise the CCLA focus (Aydin, et al. 2017).

Below, a few selected tools are presented to support the engagement of duty holders with their obligations such as the *EU4Environment Online Training on EU best practices in Environmental Compliance Assurance* and the *NetRegs Platform*, which provides environmental compliance guidance for small and medium-sized businesses. The *European Network of Prosecutors for the Environment (ENPE)* is an international non-profit organisation designed to strengthen collaboration between environmental prosecutors by helping practitioners to connect, share experiences and data on environmental crime.

Target

- Duty holders (in particular those confused or under-resourced).

Potential outcomes of the action

- Strengthen ECA system;
- Prevent non-compliance.

Examples

- [The Spanish Movement against co-incineration in their Network of Platforms Against Waste Incineration in Cement Kilns](#)
- Colonia Basilicata: Standing up against environmental degradation and neglect in Italy (see *Action Pathways*)
- Refashion textile eco-organism to foster interactions between textile waste stakeholders (see *Action Pathways*)

Selected Tools

- [EU4Environment: Online Training for Practices in Environmental Compliance Assurance](#)

- NetRegs Platform - [Environmental compliance & best practice guidance for small and medium-sized businesses](#)
- [ENPE database for environmental case law and related documents](#)
- [Environmental Compliance Handbook](#)

Additional resources

- Dubois, Maria. .Pénzesné Kónya, Erika, Martin Haigh, y Josef Křeček, eds. Environmental Sustainability Education for a Changing World. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021.
- Hoang, Anh Tuan, Abdel Rahman Al-Tawaha, Lan Anh Vu, Van Viet Pham, Ali M. Qaisi, y Josef Křeček. «Integrating Environmental Protection Education in the Curriculum: A Measure to Form Awareness of Environmental Protection for the Community». En Environmental Sustainability Education for a Changing World, 2021.
- Beveridge, Ross. «Intermediaries and networks». En The Routledge Companion to Environmental Planning. Routledge, 2019.
- Neal, Jennifer Watling, Zachary P. Neal, y Brian Brutzman. «Defining Brokers, Intermediaries, and Boundary Spanners: A Systematic Review», 2022.

3.2.2 Generate public pressure

Definition

Generate positive or negative incentives for behaviour change by generating pressure by the general public or a specific section of the population. Involves engaging with mass media, or selected channels and generating attention on a topic, or by using other rewarding mechanisms for compliant duty holders.

How can this be done?

Social pressure can be used to influence all potential CCLA targets, including duty-holders, ECA actors or policy makers. They can also be used for all CCLA purposes, and they can be designed as collaborative or confrontational interaction, or and actions confronting non-compliant duty holders can, at the same time, be shaped by collaboration with other actor groups (e.g. collaborating ECA authorities). As a result, possible actions generating public pressure are very diverse. In general, public awareness CCLAs are based either on positive or negative public pressure strategies.

In both approaches, the form and channel through which these incentives can become manifest can be similar, although the purpose may differ: as an example, engaging with the media can, in some cases, be used to celebrate successes and generate a positive public display of duty-holders, while in others, can generate public pressure and deter non-compliance by the fear of adverse publicity.

“**Positive pressure**” strategies can include promotion of “environmentally friendly” duty holders or ECA actors in general. CCLAs can provide incentives to duty-holders, emphasizing positive practices, especially those that go beyond compliance. At a broader level, this involves sharing constructive engagement and providing rewards in various forms and channels, that generate public recognition and valorise good practices (Segerson 2022), although their practical effect seems to be limited. This approach however, could present opportunities for smaller communities to act upon, when those response mechanisms may have a larger impact to capitalise good environmental practices (Conke 2023).

At civil society level, financial incentives to duty holders, certificates and other formal methods typically available to state actors are out of scope. However, supportive actions can also consist in recognizing and rewarding emerging role models or deploying community-based incentive systems (see *Comunitas Awards* in selected tools below). These approaches can also serve to counterbalance, fact-check and ultimately bring value and appropriateness of the awards offered by “accredited entities”, as the amount of those should not be taken as a definite measure of environmental performance. A different approach but in relation to these certification and label incentive-based mechanisms, is to fact-check the potential environment-friendly claims of duty-holders (Conde 2014).

“**Negative pressure**” approaches can leverage the power of public opinion, targeting various ECA actors, while pushing them to change their behaviour. Negative pressure strategies can leverage interactions with (mass) media, and various forms of activism in a wide range of actions.

Civil society actors can leverage the power of the media in various forms. This paragraph focuses on the engagement with (mass) media as an important channel than can amplify concerns or claims by communities. Engagement with the media can take place following various strategies among which we highlight the following two: actively engaging with it by means of direct contact to media channels such as news sources, or by generating attention and thus being “media-worthy” (Hanna, et al. 2016). **Active engagement** can be done by directly contacting media and informing on a certain topic, advertising in media channels, distributing press releases (for instance, linked to protest events), sending out notice of availability of representatives to be available for interviews, or press conferences. In addition, a public disclosure of violations can be a powerful tool used deliberately to obtain compliance, although it is closely related to the public access to environmental information and, of course, of compliance information (OECD 2009). The absence of this information can also be used to generate public pressure through various forms of action, and to petition duty-holders or authorities to publicly release it. Finally, active engagement with the media should carefully be evaluated in terms of timing as well as the right measure of selective use of information, as it can be counterproductive or generate rejection.

In addition, various strategies are available to **generate media attention**, such as publicity stunts, including the use of creative forms, nuisance or other more performatic elements (See *Working with Creatives* in the selected tools below). In this

regard, “events that effectively use performativity tend to be more successful in bringing their messages to the public and consequently achieving their goals” (Hanna, et al. 2016). However, “how the message is actually interpreted by the audience is beyond their control, and viewers can understand messages in different ways, and it can also create distortion”, which, together with the timeliness and selectivity of information mentioned above, are factors to evaluate prior deciding on engaging with the media. A *Collection of Tools for Effective Communication in Campaigns* and the *Public Participation Guide* are included in the selected tools sections, providing resources and strategies for engaging with the media. These tools help campaigners craft effective messages, generate public attention, and drive action through media outreach.

Various forms of non-violent protests and persuasions, non-cooperation, and non-violent interventions can be used to generate media attention, which are shown in Table 5:

Table 5 Public pressure strategies, adapted from Scheidel et al. 2020

Characteristic	Type of action
Non-violent protest and persuasion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public campaigns • Street protests • Media based activism • Artistic actions • Publicity stunts • Nuisance actions
Non-cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boycotts of (official) processes or companies and products • Strikes
Non-violent intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Occupation of public spaces

Target

- All potential targets of direct and indirect actions (duty holders, policy makers, public officials)

Potential outcomes of the action

- Respond to non-compliance;
- Supportive pressure via collaborative interactions with target (duty holders) to generate potential direct or indirect rewards.

Examples

- Recognizing compliance from ammonia neutralization efforts in Toamasina – Madagascar (see Action Pathways)
- Strengthening Indigenous governance and environmental advocacy in Bolivia (See Action Pathways)
- Environmental Awards from European Environment Foundation

- [Shemakes Reputation Management Model for Community Champions](#)
- [Sounds of the sea – Beluga Sanctuary Sealife Trust](#)
- [Defending Prey Lang: Preserving Cambodia’s Wild Legacy](#)

Selected Tools

- [Public Participation Guide: Internet Resources on Public Participation](#)
- [Working with creatives: Citizen Led Action Toolkit – CitiObs Toolkit](#)
- [Comunitas awards](#)
- Collection of tools for effective communication in campaigns:
 - [Campaign Communications Course](#), by Global Grassroots Support Network.
 - [How to Change the Narrative: Guides, Worksheets and Templates](#), by Commons Library.
 - How to Build Public Support with [Personal Stories](#), by Mobilisation Lab
 - [4 Magic Steps to Creating Shareable, Purpose-driven Social Media Content](#), by Mobilisation Lab.
 - [How to Change the Story on Social Media: ACF Community Toolkit](#), by Australian Conservation Foundation.
 - [Learn how to get covered by news media](#), by Activist Handbook.

Additional resources

- Armstrong, John H. «Public Participation and Social Movements in Environmental Policy and Justice». In *The Palgrave Handbook of Environmental Policy and Law*, 1-25. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-30231-2_19-1
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- Segerson, Kathleen. «Group Incentives for Environmental Protection and Natural Resource Management». *Annual Review of Resource Economics* 14, n.o Volume 14, 2022 (2022): 597-619.
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- Jacobsen, Grant D., Matthew J. Kotchen, and Greg Clendenning. «Community-Based Incentives for Environmental Protection: The Case of Green Electricity».

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<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11149-013-9213-z>

- Conke, L.S. (2023), "Environmental awards and their relevance to the environmental commitment of organizations", Social Responsibility Journal, Vol. 19 No. 2, pp. 344-357. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-11-2021-0477>
- The role of (environmental) taxation in supporting sustainability transitions, 2023, EEA. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/the-role-of-environmental-taxation>

3.2.3 Demand changes in environmental practices

Definition

Demand changes in environmental practices to be aligned with the "common good".

How can this be done?

Civil society actors can demand changes in environmental practices in various ways, depending on the target. These changes can formally be petitioned to institutional actors or duty holders, depending on the particular context. These type of actions in environmental compliance challenge traditional power relations: who has the power to decide about, control, allocate environmental benefits and burdens (such as distribution, access rights division of labour). The following options are available to civil society actors, in a similar categorisation as that found in *Generate public pressure*:

Table 6 Demand to change environmental practices strategies, adapted from Scheidel et al. 2020

Characteristic	Type of action
Non-violent protest and persuasion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal petitions • Development of collective action networks • Rights of nature argument • Appeals to economic valuation
Non-cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refusal of compensation
Non-violent intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) objections • Alternative proposals • Financial activism

In practical terms, the following tactical approaches show higher success rates in above mentioned actions. These insights are created after comparative analysis of the environmental conflicts and activist reactions documented in the Environmental Justice Atlas (Scheidel, et al. 2020):

- Preventive mobilisations tend to succeed in their claims versus reactive approaches, i.e. after the project or damage has been implemented or executed. Environmental mobilisations initiated in a preventive stage usually imply better awareness of the risks and access to information, knowledge and networks. This is particularly relevant for compliance promotion, as the

effectiveness of this approach points to the need to address the factor and inhibit or enable preventive mobilisation.

- Leveraging various forms of action as a tactical strategy leads to potentially higher success rates. It also “reflects on the range of skills available in the group and allows more people to participate in a diverse range of actions” and, because of that, increases pressure on duty holders, as well as the resilience of the group.
- Combining these actions with forms of litigation, including formal objections to EIAs brings in not only other forms of support, but additional points of view that support the creation of new knowledge and alternative proposals.

Target

- Duty holders;
- Environmental regulators, inspectorates and other authorities involved in implementing environmental regulation, for example by operating permit systems, monitoring and reporting on compliance levels, and enforcing regulation through administrative tools;
- Legislative bodies at all levels, from local councils to national parliaments, who are charged with the oversight of authorities and enforcement agencies and have legal rights to question and influence how formal laws are translated into agency-internal policies, strategies, and priorities.

Potential outcomes of the action

- Prevent non-compliance
- Environmental impacts through changed practice of key duty holders

Examples

- Organization of Alternatiba an event to share good practices and engage local citizens in transitions (see Action Pathways)
- Advocacy against industrial carbon emission and fossil fuel subsidies in Gijón - Spain (see Action Pathways)

Selected Tools

- [EjAtlas - Global Atlas of Environmental Justice](#)
- [Activist Handbook - Campaigning guides for activists](#)

Additional resources

- Earth First! Direct Act Manual, Third Edition. The Dam Collective, 2015. Available: https://mutualaidasterrelief.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/direct_action_manual_3-1.pdf
- Paradise Now! A Handbook for Climate Justice, Deveron Projects, 2023. Scott, A., Raheem, A., Beatriz, E., Gabrysch, F., Macdonald, H., The Huntly Youth Climate Warriors, Montserrat, J., Longdon, J., Olufemi, L., Walker, R., Bidder, R. Available: <https://goodpress.co.uk/products/paradise-now-a-climate-justice-handbook-for-young-people-edited-by-hussein-mitha>
- Phelps Bondaroff, T. N. (2015). DIRECT ENFORCEMENT ON THE HIGH SEAS: THE STRATEGY OF THE SEA SHEPHERD CONSERVATION SOCIETY [Apollo - University of Cambridge Repository]. <https://doi.org/10.17863/C.63837>
- Davies, Thom, y Alice Mah, eds. Toxic Truths: Environmental Justice and Citizen Science in a Post-Truth Age. Manchester University Press, 2020. <https://directory.doabooks.org/handle/20.500.12854/38975>
- Saunders, Clare. Environmental Networks and Social Movement Theory. Bloomsbury Academic, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781472544490>
- Apostolopoulou, Elia, Dimitrios Bormpoudakis, Alexandros Chatzipavlidis, Juan José Cortés Vázquez, Ioana Florea, Mary Gearey, Julyan Levy, et al. «Radical Social Innovations and the Spatialities of Grassroots Activism: Navigating Pathways for Tackling Inequality and Reinventing the Commons». *Journal of Political Ecology* 29, n.º 1 (5 April 2022). <https://doi.org/10.2458/jpe.2292>
- Arnim Scheidel, Daniela Del Bene, Juan Liu, Grettel Navas, Sara Mingorría, Federico Demaria, Sofía Avila, Brototi Roy, Irmak Ertör, Leah Temper, Joan Martínez-Alier, Environmental conflicts and defenders: A global overview, *Global Environmental Change*, Volume 63, 2020, 102104, ISSN 0959-3780, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2020.102104>

3.2.4 Proactive conservation and recovery actions

Definition

Physical activities to prevent, regenerate, restore or rewild.

How can this be done?

This type of action implies that civil society actors will directly engage practically by addressing the current situation with a given environmental law or regulation by volunteering to participate in conservation efforts and recover the natural environment. It can consist of, for instance, the organization and participation in

beach and ocean clean-ups, restoring or planting native habitats, removing invasive species, or the co-development of reuse and recycling solutions, in collaboration with neighbours, volunteers, with opportunities to engage with designers and potentially local Fab Labs. In addition, when these solution-driven actions are aligned with windows of opportunity to influence decision making, understood in the broader sense they can be even more impactful as they do not ‘just’ solve the issue but work towards a systemic change. Depending on the context, this action may be combined with CCLAs, in order to generate not only direct impact on the environment, but also more integral and potentially long-term outcomes (for instance, by generating public pressure, or encouraging duty holders to fulfil the obligations that led to the situation that is being remediated).

Civil society actors aiming to take a proactive part in conservation efforts can approach CCLA design following a **co-creation approach**, actively involving diverse stakeholders in the collaborative ideation and implementation of solutions for prevention, regeneration, restoration or rewilding. Such approaches should emphasize inclusivity, ensure approaches are context-specific, culturally relevant, and rooted in local needs (Eckhardt, y otros 2021). These co-creation processes can take place in participatory settings like Living Labs, where communities test and refine solutions in real-world conditions (see What is a Living Lab?), or engage with like-minded communities such as Fab Labs and the creative sector (see What is a Fab Lab?). For references on how to design a co-creation process of CCLA see the *Citizen-led Action CitiObs toolkit*, as well as the *SISCODE Toolkit* in the *Selected Tools* section below. Additional tools are listed below to facilitate realisation of (practical) actions such as using social media platforms to coordinate CCLAs, project management tools to effectively structure and oversee their implementation and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) to expand training programs to a large audience.

Finally, “proactive action” examples from different policy fields such as disaster response illustrate how interactions with networks, such as Fab Labs can be instrumental. Although disaster response is not directly linked to the ECA system, the case of ReMakeRS 2024 (see Action Pathway #2 - ReMakeRS 2024: A Maker Movement Response to Rio Grande do Sul Floods) illustrates how to take hands on action through the rapid mobilization of Fab Labs and creative communities in Brazil after the floods in Rio Grande do Sul. The ReMakeRS Emergency Challenge produced and mobilised Fab Labs across the region to design and produce open source and low-cost furniture designs to support flood victims. See the tools on *Open repositories for discovering Fab Labs worldwide* and *Open repositories to develop products for materials recycling*.

Target

- The general public. Proactive conservation and recovery actions directly contribute to the policy objectives of environmental regulation, especially related to the management of resources such as land, water, air, habitats, or biodiversity. Most environmental regulations include aspirational goals for the intended target state of environmental resources, while leaving grey areas with regard to the exact duty-holders responsible. In proactive actions, citizens self-identify as duty-holders, and accept the role as part of a collective responsibility for the intended policy outcome. By acting as role models, participating civilians aim to influence other citizens.

Potential outcomes of the action

- Direct environmental outcome
- Prevent non-compliance

Examples

- Empowering ecology ambassadors for plastic recycling in Congo (see Action Pathways)
- ReMakeRS 2024: A Maker Movement Response to Rio Grande do Sul Floods (see Action Pathways)
- The Floating Fab Lab Amazon (see Action Pathways)

Selected Tools

- [CitiObs Citizen-led Action Toolkit](#)
- Building community through social media
 - [Using Facebook Groups for organizing by Blueprints for Change](#)
 - [Social media for change by The Good Lobby](#)
 - [Social Media Activism: A guide to online change making by Jessie Mawson](#)
- [Open repository for discovering Fab Labs worldwide](#)
- Open source repositories to develop products for materials recycling
 - [Precious Plastic](#)
 - [Ultimaker](#)
 - [Opendesk](#)

Additional resources

- Eckhardt, Jennifer, Christoph Kaletka, Daniel Krüger, Karina Maldonado-Mariscal, y Ann Christin Schulz. «Ecosystems of co-creation». *Frontiers in Sociology* 6 (2021)

- «LIVING LAB: user-driven innovation for sustainability». International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education 13, n.o 2 (2012): 106-18. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14676371211211809>

3.2.5 Citizen watch and guardians

Definition

Surveillance of non-compliance either via civic data monitoring or environmental patrols. This can contribute to triggering inspections, notifying authorities of non-compliant behaviour, or deterring non-compliant behaviour directly.

How can this be done?

Depending on the ECA context, and the adequacy of authorities' response to non-compliant behaviour observed by communities, this type of CCLA can be implemented in various forms. When the ECA system has clear compliance requirements, well-defined permit systems, and **inspection** mechanisms, it is viable for individuals to directly notify authorities of non-compliant behaviour of duty holders. However, the absence of one or several of these conditions can lead citizens and communities to take on some of those tasks (i.e. **patrols**), especially when there are strong dependences or cultural and social connections to the natural resources.

Citizens and communities can act as guardians by **notifying authorities of non-compliant behaviour**. One way to do so are the *complaints* to trigger **inspections**, which are on-site visits that can reveal operational or compliance problems that monitoring data alone does not show. Adequate response to complaints is seen as a political priority in some countries. However, these complaints need to be placed in the right measure, as more inspections does not necessarily mean better detection of violations, and there is a limited capacity for the authorities to perform those inspections effectively (OECD 2009). An additional form are complaints that trigger **investigations**, which reveal generally much deeper, serious widespread or potentially continuing violations, generally of criminal nature. These investigations may be triggered by citizen complaints, or by referral from another agency. Finally, an important factor to consider is that inspections may be dependent on particular sectors of the permitting regimes and that collection of evidence may be necessary through pictures or audio-visuals, or testimonies.

Triggering these inspections or investigations may be more efficient if engaging with NGOs, experts, or in some cases, directly with environmental inspectors. These interactions can enhance knowledge acquisition by the community, and over time, this can involve comprehensive compilation of literature on a topic in collaboration with professional experts. Such relationships may be instrumentally beneficial as well, since NGOs or experts potentially have the required knowledge to report those

violations more effectively. In any case, these notifications may encounter either cooperative or non-cooperative authorities, and therefore other forms of action to generate public pressure may be required in those cases (*see Generate public pressure*, as an example).

An additional form of CCLA contributing to compliance monitoring are **community patrols**. Characteristic to these patrols is their strong connection to the local environmental resource, and their support of resource-dependent livelihoods for their economic or cultural value that leads to community organisation and mobilisation. These patrols have a strong case base on forest protection against illegal logging (connected to Community Forest Management (CFM)) (Pagdee, Kim and Daugherty 2006) and on illegal hunting. In many cases, these patrols are the only efforts to prevent illegal actions, either by lack of intent by corrupt authorities, or in illiberal democracies. Due to the complexity of the topic, practical recommendations on these patrols are out of the scope of this methodology as its likely case specific, depends heavily on the ecological, social and economic context of the local community and the status of the protection of community rights. However, a key factor at CCLA level in some contexts is the set of **community incentives and interests**, i.e. whether there is a community perception of these patrols to help the community to gain benefits or reduce costs and burdens.

Finally, significant amount of resources may be required to establish and organise these community efforts. Support from external organisations is common but other forms of collective contributions are also possible. In the *Colonia Basilicata* case (Berti Suman 2024) (*see Action Pathway* on the case), a citizen self-organised collective in the Italian region of Basilicata, the group runs a crowdfunding in an online platform (*see Open Collective* below), where they receive open financial contributions that help support their activities, for instance to buy monitoring equipment.

Target

- (opportunistic, contemptuous and criminal) non-compliant duty holders
- environmental authorities
- enforcement agencies

Potential outcomes of the action

- Diagnose non-compliance (contribution to compliance monitoring)
- Prevent infringements (direct environmental outcome);
- Strengthen ECA System.

Examples

- Colonia Basilicata: Standing up against environmental degradation and neglect in Italy (*see Action Pathways*)
- Strengthening Indigenous governance and environmental advocacy in Bolivia (*see Action Pathways*)

- Community Forest Patrols

Selected Tools

- Open Collective [Platform](#)

Additional resources

- «Civic Monitoring for Environmental Law Enforcement | Elgar Online: The online content platform for Edward Elgar Publishing». 2024. [https://www.elgaronline.com/monobook-
oa/book/9781035328703/9781035328703.xml](https://www.elgaronline.com/monobook-oa/book/9781035328703/9781035328703.xml)
- What Makes Community Forest Management Successful: A Meta-Study From Community Forests Throughout the World. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920500323260>
- In Indonesia, women ranger teams go on patrol to slow deforestation (2024, December 20) <https://apnews.com/article/aceh-indonesia-deforestation-forestry-women-rangers-83edf59f3914a512aa5031829d290d98>
- How indigenous ‘vigilante’ grandfathers protect forest life (2024, December 20) <https://www.aljazeera.com/features/2018/11/17/how-indigenous-vigilante-grandfathers-protect-forest-life/>
- Community-level responses to ‘forest violence’ in Cambodia . (2024, December 3). <https://iucn.org/news/commission-environmental-economic-and-social-policy/202109/community-level-responses-forest-violence-cambodia>
- Fighting environmental crime in Europe, Ambitus Report. (2024, December 3). https://www.iai.it/sites/default/files/ambitus_report.pdf
- Environmental Investigation Agency. (2024, December 3). <https://eia-international.org/>
- Civic resistance to environmental failures from the South (of the North...): The AnalyzeBasilicata initiative (2024, December 20) <https://data-activism.net/2018/12/civic-resistance-to-environmental-failures-from-the-south-of-the-north-the-analyzebasilicata-initiative/>

3.2.6 Denounce violations that are committed with impunity

Definition

Denounce illegal practices and/or non-compliant behaviours (social sanctions via naming & shaming). From journalism to art, including web campaigns to create public pressure on duty holders and/or enforcers.

How can this be done?

Acts that can be committed with impunity often involve illegal practices or non-compliant behaviours in environmental contexts that persist due to weak enforcement

mechanisms, low probabilities of legal action, or minimal conviction rates. These actions, such as illegal logging, pollution, or habitat destruction, are often perpetrated because the risk of being caught and held accountable is perceived as low (Cedillo and Clercq 2021). When institutions fail to effectively implement or enforce environmental laws, they inadvertently enable and even encourage such practices, creating a culture of green impunity. In this context, those engaging in harmful environmental behaviours may feel emboldened, knowing that the likelihood of facing consequences is minimal.

CCLAs can highlight these issues and draw attention to systemic inefficiencies and policy gaps. This can be done by leveraging similar strategies as those described in *Generate public pressure* as well as to leverage Information and Communication Technologies (ITCs) and the power of (social) media to generate attention on a topic, and potential become “(mass) media worthy”. These actions can be highly performatic, use satire and other forms of humour to generate further attention. Another approach can be to use existing mechanisms, such as *Whistleblowing* (see *Whistleblowing toolkit* below).

Target

- (contemptuous and criminal) non-compliant duty holders
- ECA actors targeted for their conduct

Potential outcomes of the action

- Diagnose non-compliance
- Respond to non-compliance
- Direct environmental outcome
- Policy improvement

Examples

- [Speak Up Europe against corruption](#)
- [Drinkable Rivers: How the river became my teacher](#)
- [Global Witness: denouncing violence and killings of environmental defenders across the world](#)

Selected Tools

- [Whistleblowing toolkit](#)
- [EjAtlas - Global Atlas of Environmental Justice](#)

Additional resources

- Cedillo, Celeste, y Juan Antonio Le Clercq. «Chapter 9: Green Impunity: Measuring Ecojustice, Institutional Capacities and Policy Design as an Approach to Environmental Security», 2021. <https://www.elgaronline.com/edcollchap/edcoll/9781789900651/9781789900651.00017.xml>
- Miliband, D., Affairs, C. & Group, E., 2023. *Atlas of Impunity 2023: Report*, Chicago Council on Global Affairs. United States of America. Retrieved from <https://coilink.org/20.500.12592/g5svfw> on 19 Dec 2024. DOI: [20.500.12592/g5svfw](https://doi.org/10.500.12592/g5svfw).

3.2.7 Report non-compliance to authorities

Definition

Engage with authorities to enforce legislation by reporting non-compliance.

How can this be done?

Civil society actors can interact with authorities to enforce legislation through several coordinated actions aimed at holding duty holders accountable for their obligations with respect to environmental rules and regulations. Individually, citizens can complain and report non-compliant behaviours to public authorities, especially using CGD. However, citizen alerts might trigger enforcement actions with potentially significant risks and repercussions both for deployed enforcement agents and targeted duty holders. Collaborative forums and public policy platforms offer a structured way for communities to engage directly with policymakers and authorities. In these settings, communities can present findings, share concerns regarding non-compliance of duty holders, discuss the reasons of non-compliant behaviours and suggest policy actions. These platforms can take the form of **town hall meetings, public hearings, or even advisory boards** where citizens work alongside government representatives.

Target

- (opportunistic, contemptuous and criminal) non-compliant duty holders

Potential outcomes of the action

- Respond to non-compliance
- Strengthen the ECA system

Examples

- Public campaign driving air quality reform in Poland (see Action Pathways)
- Organization of Alternatiba an event to share good practices and engage local citizens in transitions (see Action Pathways)

Selected Tools

- Collection of advocacy platforms
 - [Change.org](https://change.org) to create and promote petitions
 - [Impactive.io](https://impactive.io) to help organizations engage and mobilize their supporters through targeted actions
 - [NationBuilder](https://nationbuilder.com) to organize and manage supporters, communicate with them, and raise funds

Additional resources

- French Citizens' Convention on Climate. (2020). *Recommendations for Climate Policy*. <https://www.conventioncitoyennepourleclimat.fr/>
- Climate Case Ireland. (2020). *Landmark case against the Irish government*. <https://www.climatecaseireland.ie/>

3.2.8 Take legal actions

Definition

Sue duty holder or institutional actors and take legal action to hold them accountable for their environmental violation or inaction. Includes formal petitions to authorities to enforce legislation.

How can this be done?

“Official” mechanisms that allow civil society actors to exert pressure on government agencies can be done in court, in order to enforce regulatory requirements. Citizens have different options available to them depending on the country where they are located. For instance, direct access to courts is possible in some countries like Finland only if they are direct victims of a violation, while in other cases, they must complain to environmental authorities. In the Netherlands, citizens can petition the authorities to enforce environmental requirements and file a case in administrative court if they fail to do so (OECD 2009). This reflects the complexity of the enforcement system on each country, and how interactions with legal experts and NGOs may be necessary on each case. Additional pressure can be exerted by other means, for instance through direct mailings to authorities, or contacting environmental law enforcement.

Depending on the country where they are located, and their relationship with the environmental offense (i.e. whether they are victims or not), citizens may or may not

be able to file lawsuits directly against duty holders or bring cases to environmental courts. In some cases, when these options are not available, citizens can request regulatory authorities to take enforcement actions against violators. This type of action requires legal advice and proper situating within the legal framework in the respective country. For that reason, concrete advice is not available for all situations and is not provided in this section. In instances where evidence is presented in court, avoiding questioning of the quality of the collected data, especially when it requires technical expert knowledge for its collection, can be achieved by using simple and consistent means for collecting that data (Berti Suman, Balestrini, y otros 2023). In the case against Formosa Plastics Corporation, citizen-collected evidence involving volunteer observation of plastic pellets and powder in water was instrumental in the court ruling, and in particular, the consistency of the data collection (more than 2000 samples during more than 500 days) and the simplicity of it (photos, videos and water samples) was a key element to accept evidence in the case. In addition, the case benefited from engagement with legal experts, and their investigations (see *Citizen watch and guardians* for more details on *inspections and investigations*).

Target

- All potential targets of direct and indirect actions (duty holders, policy makers, public officials)

Potential outcomes of the action

- Respond to non-compliance;
- Strengthen the ECA system
- Policy improvement

Examples

- L'affaire du Siecle: The [Case of the Century](#)
- Protect the last remaining wild-born Spotted Owl with Ecojustice Canada (see *Action Pathways*)
- Formosa citizen suit against a giant plastics company (see *Action Pathways*)

Selected Tools

- [The United Nations Environment Programme's \(UNEP\) Guidelines for Compliance](#)

Additional resources

- Komoliddin, Halikulov. «THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF COURTS IN ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION». *International Journal Of Law And Criminology* 4, n.º 01 (2024): 71-76. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijlc/Volume04Issue01-13>

- Farid Lamara. *Droits de la nature*, s. f. <https://www.afd.fr/fr/ressources/droits-nature-hors-serie-prospective>.

3.2.9 Inhibit non-compliance via civilian interventions

Definition

Blockage of duty holder activities, occupation of sites, boycott, from non-violent to violent actions.

How can this be done?

Civil society actors can contribute to forcing duty-holders to respect laws with a spectrum of actions ranging from non-violent to more confrontational approaches, aiming to hold non-compliant duty holders accountable by preventing them to continue with their activity. Non-violent actions may include blockades of activities, where communities physically obstruct operations that harm the environment, and occupation of sites, such as taking over lands or facilities to halt illegal or ecologically harmful practices. Boycotts represent another form of resistance, targeting businesses or entities failing to comply with environmental laws by withdrawing financial or social support (Corry & Reiner, 2021). In more radical instances, actions can escalate to include disruptive tactics such as sabotage or organized civil disobedience. These efforts are often driven by a sense of urgency to protect the environment and challenge systemic failures to address climate and ecological crises (Sovacool y Dunlap 2022). While such actions highlight the intensity of environmental struggles, they underscore the need for stronger mechanisms of law enforcement and engagement to prevent escalation into violence or conflict. For this type of action, ethical consideration and boundaries of actions supported the project are of particular relevance and have to be carefully considered (see section 2.2.4).

For a review of various types of activism and further recommendations refer to *Activist action to promote enforcement* (See *Activist Handbook - Campaigning guides for activists tool*).

Target

- (Contemptuous and criminal) non-compliant duty holders

Potential outcomes of the action

- Respond to non-compliance
- Direct environmental outcome
- Strengthen the ECA system

Examples

- Advocacy against industrial carbon emission and fossil fuel subsidies in Gijón - Spain (See *Action Pathways*)
- Soulevement de la terre: [Grassroots resistance and ecological struggles](#)

Selected Tools

- [Community Rights Do-It-Yourself Guide to Lawmaking](#)
- Leveraging chat apps for coordinated environmental action
 - [Keybase](#)
 - [WhatsApp \(WhatsApp uses for campaign by Blueprint for change\)](#)
 - [Facebook Groups \(Using Facebook groups for campaign by Blueprint for change\)](#)
- Empowering activist action through mailing lists
 - [Creating Newsletters](#) by Community Tool Box
 - [Using Email Lists](#) by Community Tool Box
- CiviCRM for building, engaging [and organizing constituents](#)

Additional resources

- Davies, Thom, y Alice Mah, eds. Toxic Truths: Environmental Justice and Citizen Science in a Post-Truth Age. Manchester University Press, 2020. <https://directory.doabooks.org/handle/20.500.12854/38975>.
- Saunders, Clare. Environmental Networks and Social Movement Theory. Bloomsbury Academic, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.5040/9781472544490>
- Apostolopoulou, Elia, Dimitrios Bormpoudakis, Alexandros Chatzipavlidis, Juan José Cortés Vázquez, Ioana Florea, Mary Gearey, Julyan Levy, et al. «Radical Social Innovations and the Spatialities of Grassroots Activism: Navigating Pathways for Tackling Inequality and Reinventing the Commons». *Journal of Political Ecology* 29, n.o 1 (5 de abril de 2022). <https://doi.org/10.2458/jpe.2292>
- Arnim Scheidel, Daniela Del Bene, Juan Liu, Grettel Navas, Sara Mingorría, Federico Demaria, Sofía Avila, Brototi Roy, Irmak Ertör, Leah Temper, Joan Martínez-Alier, Environmental conflicts and defenders: A global overview, *Global Environmental Change*, Volume 63, 2020, 102104, ISSN 0959-3780, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2020.102104>

Part II Methodology for co-designing (local) citizen & community led actions

In the second part of this deliverable, we describe the *initial* more4nature CCLA co-design methodology. After situating CCLAs in more4nature in part I, we now focus on providing guidance and case-based inspiration to the users of this methodology. After this introduction, part II is structured as follows:

1. *CCLA co-design methodology*: aiming to provide a synthesis of CCLA generic guidance to support decisions on a broader setting and a set of customized co-design tools, which support focusing on the case context, defining a shared goal and target for the co-designed CCLAs.
2. *Action pathways*: Next, examples of real-world CCLA strategies are provided as inspiration, which contains a compilation of cases with links to recommendations and practical tools and resources in the Annex. The Action Pathways can be visited at any time, either at earlier ideation stages, or further into the implementation process or in an iterative manner.
3. *Working with Living Labs and Fab Labs*: *targeting specific guidance and recommendations on how to establish connections with Living Labs and Fab Labs.*

In essence, the more4nature CCLA co-design methodology is intended to be as *comprehensive as needed, and as down-to-earth as possible*. Therefore, the methodology aims to keep a limited degree of tentativeness at its core and embraces the fact that there is no *one-size-fits-all recipe* for all the cases and contexts available within more4nature or elsewhere. To support this approach, the methodology is structured to provide practical guidance in both the co-design process and to interact and potentially build relationships with Living Labs and Fab Labs, while providing inspiration via Action Pathways. This approach allows the more4nature case stakeholders to visit guidance at different stages of their co-design process, which is iterative in nature and will understandably evolve throughout the process in different ways for each particular case, as they also interact with other more4nature tasks, under the overarching guidance of T3.1.

However, as flexible as this guidance may be, there is an intrinsic link to a case's context that the CCLA co-design process requires when seeking to have a meaningful impact on the different pillars of collaborative ECA or the policy making cycle. In this sense, we provide a set of *Co-design Cards* intended to play a more central role in the CCLA co-design methodology, which then allows for diversification in action. The reasoning behind these tools is that the CCLA co-design process draws from an ECA issue that has already been identified, and which needs to be situated in the case context, including an identifiable legal framework, a target and a group of actors. To maximize the CCLA impact, this ECA issue is then linked to a clear idea on the intended outcome, either aiming to potentially revert a situation that under the existing legal framework should not have happened, or to influence the policy cycle that led to that legal framework. This approach aims to solve the identified ECA issue and have a systemic impact. This understanding of the context will then be the base

that serves us to explore options for action and where the Action pathways will aim to provide inspirational guidance.

Therefore, the approach focuses on connecting with the case context in order to facilitate the conscious choice between multiple *Action pathways*, which ideally lands on a co-designed *pathway* that aims to solve both, the ECA issue at hand, and to ideally strengthen the ECA system. Then, to provide specific support to cases on the CCLA co-design process, the *Guidance* starts with tools that show 1) how to *explore potential resources as suitable courses of action in the case's context*, 2) *identify suitable CCLA targets and strategies*, 3) *engage with external actors and networks such as Living Labs and Fab Labs*, and 4) *access tools that provide real-world guidance* (aimed at further complementing the practical steps of each action pathway, which can be navigated freely). To facilitate the choice, these tools are referenced throughout the different sections of this methodology, such as the *Landscape of Actions* or the *Action pathways*, as applicable.

1 CCLA co-design methodology

This section provides the practical steps of the CCLA co-design methodology. First, we detail the overall approach, drawing from the analysis presented in part I, but focusing on the practical aspects. Next, to situate the issue triggering civil society action and driving the goal of the future CCLA, a series of co-design cards is presented, which also facilitates getting started with the CCLA co-design methodology. Finally, we describe how to liaise with Living Labs and Fab Labs in the co-design process of a CCLA. In the context of more4nature, the implementation of this co-design methodology is applied as part of T3.5.

Two main stages are identified as part of the CCLA co-design methodology for the more4nature cases: *getting started* and *implementation*. This distinction is aimed at first removing barriers to the first steps in the co-design of CCLAs, and then, to facilitate their implementation and iterations if needed:

- *Getting started with the CCLA co-design methodology*: To facilitate the onboarding of more4nature case stakeholders to the CCLA co-design methodology, a series of cards has been designed to facilitate their initial reflection process. These cards aim to convey the concept of CCLA in an accessible format, helping users to situate their motivations to act and take the first steps in their CCLA co-design process. This is shown in Figure 5 and the cards are detailed below with further elaborations.
- *Implementation of the CCLA*: Once users have decided to implement their CCLA, a set of tools is provided to help them plan and organise their action, by designing their own Action Pathway, and to monitor progress, measure impact and compare it to their initially expected goals. Once using these cards, partners are invited to iterate and revisit previous steps of the getting started stage, if necessary.

Peer-exchange sessions and adapted support (as part of task T3.5) will be proposed to the more4nature partners to facilitate the appropriation of the methodology and the co-design and implementation of the actions.

Figure 5 Co-design Methodology overview

Source: the authors

1.1 CCLA Co-design cards

A series of cards have been designed to support more4nature case stakeholders in the design and planning of their future CCLAs. These tools are “meta/design”-tools, in that they are aimed at supporting the case stakeholders in thinking how they will design their own Action Pathway. Aligned with the guidance, five cards were created to onboard partners in planning their actions: the *Issue Card*, the *CCLA ecosystem Card*, the *CCLA Goal Card*, the *Define your own Action Pathway Card* and the *Measure CCLA Impact Card*. These CCLA co-design cards are accessible in pdf format to print (Annex III) or to be used digitally on an interactive board.

1.1.1 CCLA Issue card

The Issue Card is aimed at better understanding the situation of the issue triggering an action and the status of the current ECA situation. On this card, partners are invited to first define the issue they face, who are the duty holders, what is the current compliance situation and discuss existing community initiatives addressing the issue. An important point is allocated to identifying the reasons why the issue is happening: what are the attitudes and motivations of duty holders, and whether the responsibilities and obligations are clear and enforceable.

Figure 6: CCLA Context Card

1.1.2 CCLA Ecosystem Card

After situating the context of the issue, by using the Ecosystem card, more4nature case stakeholders can reflect on whether they want to target duty holders, policy makers or ineffective ECA actors. Users are invited to explore the core stakeholders that will be involved in the Citizen and Community-Led Action, their motivations to act on the situation as well as external partners to liaise with.

Figure 7: CCLA Ecosystem card

1.1.3 CCLA Goal Card

The *CCLA Goal Card* is aimed at supporting partners in defining the goal of their CCLA, first by reflecting on the purpose of the action (supportive or critical), the interactions with the target (collaborative or confrontational) and the type of action. A visual positioning of the action, a brief narrative description of the overall goal of the CCLA and selection of intended outcomes (from a pre-defined list) will help users clarify and capture the goal of their CCLA.

3. CCLA GOAL CARD

Purpose

What are the main purposes(s) of your planned action?

Supportive
Directed towards targets who are confused, careless or under-resourced, serves to change their behaviour by sharing the knowledge and resources available to them.

Critical
Directed towards targets who are opportunistic, contemptuous or cynical, serves to influence their behaviour and decisions by generating social and institutional pressures.

Action Types

Situate yourself among the types of CCLAs

- Assist duty holders to encourage compliance
- Generate public pressure
- Demand changes in environmental practices
- Pro-active conservation and recovery actions
- Organise citizen patrols & watch
- Denounce violations committed with impunity
- Report non-compliance to authorities
- Take legal action
- Inhibit non-compliance via civilian interventions

SITUATE YOUR CCLA

Interaction with target

CCLA STATEMENT

Please briefly describe the goal of your action

Interactions

What is the interaction with the target of the action and with relevant public authorities? (please tick corresponding box(es))

	Interactions with Target (tick)	Interactions with Public Authority (tick)	Interactions with Public Authority (tick)	Interactions with Public Authority (tick)
Collaborative	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Confrontational	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Outcomes

Which outputs/outcomes are you aiming for?

- Prevent non-compliance
- Diagnose non-compliance
- Respond to non-compliance
- Direct environmental outcome
- Policy improvement
- Strengthen the ECA system
- Other (please specify)

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UK participants in Horizon Europe Project more4nature are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10106632 UNEP-WCNC and 10110900 Earthwatch Europe.

Figure 8: Goal Card

1.1.4 Define your own Action Pathway Card

Based on the logic of the *Action Pathways* described in Chapter 2, this card is supporting users in planning their CCLA. They start by envisioning a series of steps they would need to implement the CCLA in order to achieve the goal and purpose (as defined on the *Goal card*). Once they have drawn a first draft of their process, they can analyse what skills and resources are needed at each step to implement the action. Finally, partners can consult tools that may be useful for their particular *Action Pathway*, define what partnerships they may need to create to fill in knowledge and skills gaps they might have.

Figure 9: Define your own Action Pathway Card

1.1.5 Measuring CCLA impact card

The *CCLA Impact card* invites users to define and measure the impact of their CCLA on both, external and internal outcomes of their co-designed CCLA. This card also raises their attention to future steps, by inviting them to reflect on possible adaptations to their strategy for implementing the CCLA (in the short and in the long term) and whether additional CCLAs are needed (to achieve their goal and/or due to changes in the context).

5. MEASURE CCLA IMPACT CARD more4nature
with citizen science

	<p style="text-align: center; margin: 0;">DEFINE</p> <p style="font-size: small; margin: 0;">What impact do you want to create with your action? What would make it a success? What specific internal or external outcomes are you aiming for?</p>	<p style="text-align: center; margin: 0;">MEASURE</p> <p style="font-size: small; margin: 0;">What is the actual impact of the action(s)? What can you learn from this experience?</p>	<p style="text-align: center; margin: 0;">NEXT</p> <p style="font-size: small; margin: 0;">What adaptations does your strategy need, in the short or long term? What other CCLAs may need to be implemented?</p>
<p>INTERNAL OUTCOMES</p> <p style="font-size: x-small;">Sense of urgency & achievement, capacity, skills, resources, sense of collective</p>			
<p>EXTERNAL OUTCOMES</p> <p style="font-size: x-small;">Prevent non-compliance Diagnose non-compliance Respond to non-compliance Direct environmental actions Policy improvement Strengthen the ECA system Other (please specify)</p> <p style="font-size: x-small;">Remember to check your CCLA Goal Card</p>			

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101133963.

 UK participation in Horizon Europe Project milestones are supported by UKRI grant numbers: 10156103 UNEP-RECIC and 10119893 Earthwatch Europe

Figure 10: Measure CCLA impact card

2 Action Pathways

In the context of more4nature, Citizen and Community-Led Actions are interventions driven by individual citizens or groups aiming to protect the environment. In part I we have elaborated on these definitions with factors that further characterise CCLAs as context-based, dynamic and iterative processes that involve engagement of specific actors, the definition of a target, and that can take various forms and temporal durations. CCLAs evolve as the individuals or communities also evolve in their collective processes by developing relationships, gaining knowledge or trust. Moreover, there is a “repertoire” of routines that CCLAs can build upon.

To support skill acquisition and inspiration for designing and implementing CCLAs, we developed a **repertoire of Action Pathways** that more4nature case stakeholders can use as **inspiration and living knowledge** about the diversity of possible paths to take toward the co-design of CCLA in the context of ECA. This repertoire not only showcases real-world examples from a variety of contexts, but presents them from an implementation perspective, so that users easily reflect on their own possibilities and resources. In addition, this highlights that there is **no single recipe for CCLAs in the context of ECA**, and that different factors affect their development (and hence how to design them), which implies that the creation of a prescriptive methodology is not possible nor necessary.

This repertoire is produced initially based on desk research, but it is intended to evolve throughout the more4nature project lifetime, and it is stored on an online Miro board, which is accessible to more4nature project partners, and will be made openly available later on in the project.

2.1 What is an Action Pathway?

An *Action Pathway* is a simplified way to represent the different steps that compose a CCLA in the context of ECA, using distinct blocks organized in a visual way. Its aim is to trace the development and deployment path of a CCLA, from its inception to its deployment, while emphasizing the core resources and determinants of the most important steps in the process.

In practical terms, an *Action Pathway* is a schematic representation that can be drawn on paper or in interactive board using simple blocks (Figure 11). The Action Pathway for CCLA is composed of five components:

- **ECA situation and stakeholders:** each Action Pathway is initiated with a short representation of the ECA situation and core stakeholders present in the action.
- **Action title:** represented in a circle marking the beginning of the pathway.
- **Process:** A vertical process, displayed on the left of the diagram, decomposing the Action Pathway into a series of sub-activities that are related to each other. A main linear path of action is traced with boxes and arrows, completed by

feedback arrows that illustrate the iterative dimension of the action pathway when it is relevant for a case. Each step is meant to represent a simple process.

- **Resource and Skills:** Next to the *Process*, in the center of the diagram, this section highlights what type of competences, infrastructure, expertise was needed during each step of the pathways.
- **Tools and Guidance:** Finally, on the right side of the diagram, a series of tools and recommendations are listed to facilitate possible replication of the Action Pathways in other contexts.

Figure 11: Action Pathway overview

2.2 Towards an Action Pathways Repertoire

Our ambition is to compile an *Action Pathways Repertoire of CCLAs for ECA* from diverse contexts. The repertoire will be composed of exemplary or inspirational actions, from literature cases to more4nature cases.

- **Exemplary action pathways** are those that relate directly to the context of environmental compliance, serving to illustrate the process and resources underlying each type of action.
- **Inspirational action pathways**, on the contrary, although still CCLAs, these inspirational action pathways present examples that have taken place in contexts other than compliance, and that are inspirational in the ways of engaging stakeholders, co-creating with citizens and communities or consolidating partnerships with external actors like Fab Labs and Living Labs.

At the moment of writing this deliverable, the *Repertoire of Action Pathways* contains a set of 12 examples that serve as inspiration for the more4nature case stakeholders. In addition, the experimental nature of this approach aims to use this initial repertoire as a testbed to improve the current design and relevance of the *Action Pathways*, which will be evaluated in the context of T3.5 (i.e. including the interim evaluation of the implementation of this CCLA co-design methodology).

The current *Repertoire of Action Pathways* can be found on a Miro board. Additions to the board are possible upon access request to the board owners. More4nature partners will be encouraged to design and upload new examples, based on their own experience as part of T3.2.

Table 7 Current Repertoire of Action Pathways for CCLAs presents an overview of the current selection of *Action Pathways*. In this deliverable, we include more detailed descriptions of 3 examples, to showcase their principle, while the online *repertoire* contains all examples.

Table 7 Current Repertoire of Action Pathways for CCLAs

Title	CCLA Purpose	Type of Interactions with Targets	Action Pathway
The Floating FAB LAB Amazon	Supportive	Collaborative	Inspirational
ReMakeRS 2024: A Maker Movement Response to Rio Grande do Sul Floods	Supportive	Collaborative	Inspirational
Public campaign driving air quality reform in Poland	Critical	Confrontational	Exemplary
Recognizing compliance from ammonia neutralization efforts in Toamasina - Madagascar	Supportive	Collaborative	Exemplary
Refashion a textile eco-organism to foster interactions between textile waste stakeholders	Supportive	Collaborative	Inspirational
Organization of Alternatiba an event to share good practices and engage local citizens in transitions	Supportive	Collaborative	Inspirational
Colonia Basilicata: Standing up against environmental degradation and neglect in Italy	Critical	Collaborative	Exemplary
Strengthening Indigenous and governance	Supportive	Collaborative	Exemplary

Title	CCLA Purpose	Type of Interactions with Targets	Action Pathway
environmental advocacy in Bolivia			
Protect the last remaining wild-born Spotted Owl with Ecojustice Canada	Supportive	Collaborative	Inspirational
Formosa citizen suit against a giant plastics company	Critical	Confrontational	Exemplary
Advocacy against fossil fuel subsidies in Gijón - Spain	Critical	Confrontational	Exemplary
Empowering ecology ambassadors for plastic recycling in Congo	Supportive	Collaborative	Inspirational

Source: the authors

2.3 Action Pathways showcase

2.3.1 Action Pathway #1 - Empowering ecology ambassadors for plastic recycling in Congo

CCLA Purpose: Supportive.

Type of Interaction between Actors and Targets: Collaborative.

The Couronne Verte project⁸ was initiated by the French embassy in Congo, in collaboration with various stakeholders including Union Fab Lab in Brazzaville, local associations and foreign universities, works to promote plastic reduction and recycling, given the lack of national regulations on the matter. Given the severity of local pollution, including plastic waste, the program includes raising awareness on the need to reduce plastic consumption, and provides training to young adults in plastic collection, classification and recycling, using machines to transform them and, for instance, to create 3D printed filament from those items, or to make furniture with it. It organizes training for more than 30 students per year and has been operating for 3 years. While the initiative depends on public-private partnerships and external funding, it faces challenges, including limited local government support, financial constraints, and cultural resistance when it has gone beyond Brazzaville and engage with other affected communities, near the Congo Basin.

ECA Situation & CCLA stakeholders

⁸ Couronne Verte Website: <https://www.adiac-congo.com/content/couronne-verte-le-rendez-vous-des-ambassadeurs-de-lecologie-au-congo-138113>

Process, Resources & skills and, Tools & Guidance

Process

Required skills/resources

Tools and guidance

2.3.2 Action Pathway #2 - ReMakeRS 2024: A Maker Movement Response to Rio Grande do Sul Floods

CCLA Purpose: Supportive.

Type of Interaction between Actors and Targets: Collaborative.

In response to the devastation caused by heavy rains, exacerbated by climate change in Rio Grande do Sul – Brazil in late April and early May 2024, Fab Labs and creative communities have mobilized to address urgent needs through innovative, collective efforts. Local Fab Labs began prototyping tools, such as large squeegees, to aid in the cleaning of mud-filled homes. This effort quickly expanded into a broader initiative: an Emergency Design Challenge⁹ inviting designers, makers, architects, and carpenters to develop open-source, low-cost, and easily replicable furniture for flood victims. The initiative combines grassroots creativity with structured methodologies, including clear design criteria, open-source accessibility, and awards for the best projects in various categories. Communications and media strategies were used to amplify its reach, attracting the attention of policymakers and showcasing the potential of the maker movement to drive impactful collective action.

ECA Situation & CCLA stakeholders

⁹ Information about the Initiative ReMakers 2024: <https://www.unisinos.br/noticias/remakers-o-desafio-de-design-emergencial-que-ajudara-familias-atingidas-pelas-enchentes/>

Process, Resources & skills and, Tools & Guidance

Process

Required skills/resources

Tools and guidance

2.3.3 Action Pathway #3 - Advocacy against industrial carbon emission and fossil fuel subsidies in Gijón - Spain

CCLA Purpose: Critical.

Type of Interaction between Actors and Targets: Confrontational.

A series of protests in Gijón highlights community-led efforts to address the environmental harm caused by fossil fuel industries. Activists in Asturias, aligned with the 'European Stop EU Fossil Subsidies campaign', organized a peaceful blockade of factory trucks to raise awareness about the environmental impact of high CO₂ emissions and pollutants linked to the industry. Despite receiving €450 million in government subsidies for decarbonization, the company in question has been criticized for failing to take sufficient action to reduce its environmental footprint. The protest, which led to legal charges and calls for compensation, has gotten solidarity from environmental groups and citizens who are calling for more accountability in the use of public funds for fossil fuel industries. This action underscores the urgent need for systemic change and greater responsibility in how subsidies are allocated and how corporations tackle the climate crisis.

ECA Situation & CCLA stakeholders

Process, Resources & skills and, Tools & Guidance

Process

Required skills/resources

Tools and guidance

3 Working with Living Labs and Fab Labs

As mentioned in part I, an important factor to the more4nature approach is the potential interactions that civil society actors can establish with external networks and institutions. Two specific connections are being sought in terms of networking within the CCLAs in more4nature: their potential connection with Living Labs and with artists, place makers and makerspaces and networks, such as the global network of Fab Labs. Connections with the creative sector, such as artists, designers and place makers, can be facilitated by the *Citizen-led Action toolkit*¹⁰ (CitiObs Project), that introduces practical tools for *Working with Creatives*, emphasizing how the arts and creative practices can drive collaborative action. Complementary to previous sections, and the CitiObs project approach, this section explores how civil society actors can engage with Living Labs and Fab Labs as key spaces that can support their CCLA co-design process.

3.1 Living Labs

3.1.1 What is a Living Lab?

Living Labs are research and innovation hubs that operate as “third spaces”, developing and testing technologies, products, and services in real-world settings through co-creation with citizens, businesses, governments, and research organizations (Hossain, Leminen and Westerlund 2019). The origins of Living Labs trace back to the 1970s in Scandinavia, where early experiments with cooperative design incorporated user involvement. During the 1980s and 1990s, digital initiatives across Europe began linking citizens, businesses, and policymakers. The term “Living Lab” surfaced in academic discussions in the 1990s, but it gained prominence in 2006 when the European Commission launched an initiative to establish a Common European Innovation System based on Living Labs (Leminen and Westerlund 2019).

Living Labs are dedicated to creating user-centred and open innovation ecosystems, being frequently hosted in universities, municipalities, and research institutions. With access to such infrastructures, projects connected to Living Labs enable the rapid prototyping, testing, and scaling of innovative solutions. These labs are commonly employed in areas such as urban planning, energy efficiency, healthcare, information management and digital media (Baran and Berkowicz 2020). While Living Labs often emphasize urban settings and the acceleration of innovation and business development, a review of the literature reveals that they have also been applied to climate change mitigation and sustainable natural resource management. These efforts extend to areas such as zero pollution initiatives, biodiversity conservation, and contributions to the bioeconomy sector. (Lakatos, et al. 2024) (Woods y Berker 2019) (Bouma 2022).

¹⁰ CitiObs Toolkits: <https://citiobs.eu/toolkits>

With the mission of facilitating knowledge exchange, joint actions, and project partnerships, the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL) was established in 2006 as a non-profit association of over 480 Living Labs worldwide. ENoLL promotes Living Labs as environments for real-life testing and experimentation, supporting open innovation among citizens, government, industry, and academia (the Quadruple Helix Model). The network facilitates knowledge exchange, project partnerships, and advocacy to strengthen the impact of Living Labs and influence innovation policies at the EU and global levels.

3.1.2 Living Labs CCLA cases

As a general principle of being platforms that enable participation in innovation processes, users who are willing to participate in real-life experimentation environment should be easily included in a Living Lab setting. Following a quadruple helix model, citizens and communities play an important role in promoting civic activism by nurturing projects related to social innovation. In the context of environmental protection, a few cases can be exemplified by the interaction of living labs for fostering citizen and community led actions. The NB-Lab (Nature-Based Living Lab¹¹) operates in the Amazon Rainforest, establishing interdisciplinary research hubs in Tena, Ecuador, and Iquitos, Peru to support sustainable rural communities' development through the preservation and responsible use of the natural resources in the Amazonian Region. Also, in the topic of resource management, tailored methodologies have been developed and applied to establish Living Labs in the EU MAR2PROTECT project¹², where workshops engage stakeholders in co-creating innovative solutions for protecting groundwater from the impacts of climate change and global change.

Through the European Union's Mission: "A Soil Deal for Europe" 100 Living Labs and Lighthouses are planned to be created by 2030 initiatives, aiming at fostering sustainable land and soil management. With this programme, the EU seeks to improve soil health and promote biodiversity, contributing significantly to the European Green Deal's objectives of sustainability and environmental restoration.

3.1.3 How to work with Living Labs

To initiate collaboration with Living Labs, a first step is to identify relevant Living Labs acting on the topic of interest. A potential identification can be done by exploring the ENoLL Member Catalogue (Tricarico, et al. 2023), which lists active Living Labs within the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL). This catalogue provides key information about each lab's focus areas, ongoing projects, and contact details. After identifying relevant labs, direct contact can be made with the respective contact points or through the ENoLL coordination team outlining the case objectives and explain how

¹¹ Nature-Based Living Lab website: <http://www.nb-lab.info/>

¹² EU MAR2PROTECT project website: <https://mar2protect.eu/>

the collaboration could contribute to the Living Lab's ongoing initiatives. In cases where direct contact is not feasible or further support is required, assistance can be done through IAAC, facilitating connections with the appropriate Living Lab coordinators within the ENoLL network.

Engagement and collaboration with LL partners in the context of ENoLL can also take place through the participating in working groups and during the ENoLL annual event. For the joint working groups, ENoLL members and selected external stakeholders can participate in regular discussions designed to foster knowledge exchange and peer debate. A few relevant thematic areas for more4nature are digital sustainability for zero pollution and energy and environment. In respect to the OpenLivingLab Days¹³, the flagship annual event organized by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), participants can join conferences, research sessions, hands-on workshops, and interactive discussions for networking, exchanging best practices, and collaborating on specific projects.

3.2 Fab Labs

3.2.1 What is a Fab Lab?

The Fab Charter¹⁴ describes Fab Labs as “a global network of local labs, enabling invention by providing access to tools for digital fabrication,” as an infrastructure to “share an evolving inventory of core capabilities to make (almost) anything, allowing people and projects to be shared.” This global network has a proven capacity for collaborative educational endeavours through the worldwide distributed courses of Fab Academy¹⁵, Fabricademy¹⁶ and Bio Academy¹⁷ and also their involvement at both the local and global level for the initiatives such as the FabXEvents¹⁸, Fab Research¹⁹, Fab City Global Initiative²⁰, the Resilience Collective²¹, Fab Economy²² and Fab Lab House²³.

In the online environment, the global network showcases its collaborative approach through the Fab Foundation Forum, which facilitates communication, knowledge sharing and collaboration between regional networks, and the fablabs.io²⁴ platform (the online social network of the international Fab Lab Community) which provides a

¹³ OpenLivingLab Days website: <https://openlivinglabdays.com/>

¹⁴ Fab Charter: <https://fab.cba.mit.edu/about/charter/>

¹⁵ Fab Academy site: <https://fabacademy.org/>

¹⁶ Fabricademy site: <https://fabricademy.org/>

¹⁷ Bio Academy site: <https://bio.academany.org/>

¹⁸ FabXEvents website: <https://fabevent.org/>

¹⁹ Access to Fab Research library: <https://library.fabfoundation.org/>

²⁰ Fab City Global Initiative website: <https://fab.city>

²¹ The Resilience Collective Website: <https://resilience-collective.com/>

²² Fab Economy Website: <https://fabfoundation.github.io/fabeconomy/>

²³ Information about the Fab Lab House: <https://iaac.net/project/fab-lab-solar-house/>

²⁴ Fablabs.io website: <https://fablabs.io>

map with all the official nodes around the world, guidelines, machine information and other resources open accessible to the global community.

Central to Fab Labs is a participatory way of working, which arises due to its connections to three characteristics that creates a common narrative around the maker culture including “a strong emphasis on learning through hands-on creation, a transdisciplinary approach due to the different backgrounds of the people involved, and a strong ethos that knowledge should be freely accessible” (O’Duinn, F., 2012 as cited in (Troxler 2016)).

Fab Labs serve as collaborative platforms that embody values of collaboration, decentralization, participation, and democratization of technology. They play diverse roles, including learning spaces for skill development and STEM education through hands-on activities, manufacturing hubs for prototyping and refining innovative solutions, and service providers offering rapid prototyping for customized products. Additionally, Fab Labs foster interdisciplinary collaboration by attracting diverse expertise and promoting open innovation. As community hubs, they facilitate local and global engagement ("glocal" impact) through workshops, hackathons, and projects, leveraging their integration into a global network of over 2.500 Fab Labs in 125 countries.

3.2.2 Fab Labs CCLA cases

Fab Labs have shared principles and values to those found in many CS initiatives, and the proactive attitude of many Fab Labs worldwide can be a strong driver for collaboration between them. One example is the Making Sense project²⁵, which focused on exploring how open-source software, and hardware, digital maker practices and open design can be effectively used by local communities to fabricate their own sensing tools, make sense of their environments and address pressing environmental problems in air and sound pollution. The project led to the consolidation of air quality monitoring tools in Fab Labs, such as the Smart Citizen Project²⁶ which empower citizens to track air quality in their environments, as well as creating CS methodologies like the Citizen Sensing Toolkit²⁷. Another example is the Citizen Science initiative Puffin Patrol led by Fab Lab Vestmannaeyjar²⁸ in Iceland for biodiversity protection. The project combines biodiversity monitoring with the development of prototype tracking devices for birdlife and integrates educational activities to engage the local community in conservation efforts. A third example is a project in Congo, launched by the French embassy, which focuses on plastic reduction and recycling. In collaboration with Union Fab Lab²⁹, local associations, and universities, the initiative trains young

²⁵ Making Sense EU Project website: <https://making-sense.eu/>

²⁶ Smart Citizen Project website: <https://smartcitizen.me/>

²⁷ Access to the Citizen Sensing Toolkit: <https://making-sense.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Citizen-Sensing-A-Toolkit.pdf>

²⁸ Fab Lab Vestmannaeyjar website: <https://fablab.is/starfsstodvar/vestmannaeyjar/>

²⁹ Information about the Union Fab Lab: <https://www.fablabs.io/labs/unionlab>

adults in plastic recycling, machine use, and the creation of 3D printed filament from recycled plastic, encouraging local solutions to waste management challenges (see Action Pathway #1). In all these cases, Fab Labs have played a multifaceted role, that evolved as trust relationships improved among collaborators, leading to long lasting relationships (in some cases of more than ten years, such as the Iceland case in Biodiversity conservation).

3.2.3 How to work with Fab Labs

CS Initiatives can collaborate with Fab Labs by tapping into the different labs' capabilities for education, social innovation, rapid prototyping, and community engagement.

After identifying the interest or need to work with such actors, the **first step is to identify local Fab Labs** (potentially with an interest on environmental protection). This can be done through fablabs.io³⁰, (the online social network of the international Fab Lab Community) which provides a map with all the official nodes around the world, guidelines, machine information and other resources open accessible to the global community. Once some relevant Fab Labs have been explored or identified, preparations for a **first communication** may be started. For this first communication, direct means may be used, as many Fab Labs share their contact information through fablabs.io, but a more indirect approach may be preferred, with assistance provided by IAAC, which facilitates connections with the relevant Fab Lab coordinators within the global Fab Labs network. Finally, IAAC is also working on establishing a formal working group through the fablabs.io forum, which can be an entry point in future cases.

An important hybrid platform for getting in contact with the Fab Lab network and getting to know the state-of-art from project in different fields, from disruptive technology to prevention and mitigation of environmental disasters, is the Fab Event, the annual conference of Fab Labs. The event organized by the Fab Foundation, a non-profit organization from the MIT's Center for Bits and Atoms³¹, brings together innovators, educators, scientists, policy makers and community leaders, to explore the power of digital fabrication for transformative change.

In preparation for this first communication, a **presentation brief** is recommended for the Fab Lab to understand the needs and potential synergies. This brief does not need to be formal, but it must spark motivation for the Fab Lab members to understand their involvement and feel engaged to contribute. Recommendations on these aspects are:

- Focus on explaining the impact on the (local) community and environment
- Be clear on what the envisioned role of the Fab Lab may be

³⁰ FabLabs.io Website: <https://www.fablabs.io/>

³¹ Center for Bits and Atoms at MIT website: <https://cba.mit.edu/>

- Do not hesitate to ask if an in-person visit to the Fab Lab is possible

In addition, the following series of questions can help start shaping the potential interaction and build a collective understanding (X):

- What is the envisioned Fab Lab's role? Questions like the following will help us define this:
 - Will their role be more strategic, conceptual and open ended, more focused on facilitating events and activities, or developing creative outputs?
 - Will they work with the members from within the CS Initiatives, or will their role be more public facing, or focused on working with specific communities?
- What level of experience is required? Questions like the following will help us define this:
 - Does the scope or scale of the CCLA require someone with a significant level of experience, or would it be equally suited to a newer Fab Lab member?)
- What are the skills being sought? Questions like the following will help us define this:
 - Is it required to have experience of designing and facilitating workshops?
 - Are skills and training in a particular technique needed?
 - Is experience of working in specific contexts needed? (e.g. working with communities, in academic and research contexts, within organisations or with policy makers)
- What are the desired outcomes?

This process may as well be done in collaboration with the Fab Lab once a first contact has been established.

4 Conclusions and next steps

This report has introduced the initial more4nature methodology for co-designing Citizen and Community-Led Actions in ECA contexts with civil society stakeholders, and in collaboration with Living Labs and Fab Labs.

The conceptualisation of CCLAs in the context of collaborative ECA provided in Part I will serve as a reference point for the more4nature consortium – and especially for the work of the more4nature case contacts with case stakeholders - on the potential role of civil society actors in ECA via supportive or critical actions. The Typology of Actions provides the (civil society) case stakeholders with a structured overview of CCLAs that can empower citizens and communities and create spaces in which society actors can play an active role in Environmental Compliance Assurance.

The detailed guidance provided for the CCLA co-design process in Part II, along with references to relevant tools and resources, will help develop specific *Action Pathways* in relevant more4nature cases, i.e. in Pioneer cases and Follower cases, via task T3.5 Co-designing (local) actions. Concretely, the CCLA strategies compiled here, in the form of a living repertoire of CCLA *Action Pathways* based on real-world examples, serve as inspiration for civil society stakeholders in more4nature cases.

On a practical level, the CCLA co-design guidance provided in Part II of this report will be carefully integrated into the case compendia that are coordinated by T3.1 *Methodology for Double Loop Action Research* and which serve to structure and ensure the coherent implementation of the more4nature case methodology presented in deliverable D3.1 (Wehn and Pfeiffer 2024).

Feedback and inputs from the application of the initial CCLA co-design methodology to be collected by T3.3 *Reflection on the first cycle and refinement* and by T3.7 *Co-evaluation and synthesis*, will serve to refine it and to produce the final version of the more4nature CCLA co-design methodology. This final version of the methodology will be delivered towards the end of the more4nature project as deliverable D1.8, in month 46 (October 2027).

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Annexes

Annex I

Table A 1 Citizen and Community-Led Actions in collaborative ECA by more4nature partners. Results from the workshop in Copenhagen. Plenary meeting, May 2024.

Country	Action Title	Citizen Action Scenario	Description of activities
Poland	Air Pollution in Poland	Engage entities with environmental impact to encourage compliance to targets	Signed petition made by NGO to assure policy makers that the regulation has citizen support;
		Engage authorities to enforce set targets	In parallel, conversations with relevant politicians
		Engage with media to generate attention about the topic	NGOs fed local media with relevant information for citizens - accesibility
			Social media campaigns supporting local media
		Take solution-driven practical action	Billboards around Krakow (provided by owner of media agency for free)
		(radical) Activist action	NGO organized public marches staged as the funeral of Clean Air to the Parliament (supported by local artists)
Norway	Free flowing rivers (Amber app)	Engage entities with environmental impact to encourage compliance to targets	NJFF (norwegian hunter and fishing organisation) engaged with hydropower company (Lyse) to finance measures for barrier removal / restoration
			Sea trout project restoration activities (collaboration with different organisations)
		Engage authorities to enforce set targets	NJFF (norwegian hunter and fishing organisation) engaging with the Norwegian Environment Agency to encourage removal of specific barriers
		Engage with media to generate attention about the topic	In order to create awareness about the app and how to register barriers for citizens (related to data collection but also the issue itself + consequences) - norways hunter and fisher organisation and the biodiversity organisation Sabima together with NIVA researchers engaged with media (press release) resulting in stories in news papers and radio
		Take solution-driven practical action	NJFF (norwegian hunter and fishing organisation) have themselves removed barriers in fishing rivers

		Encourage responsible authority/policy maker	A group of NGOs, in collaboration with several municipalities, point to shortcomings in the Norwegian government's follow-up of the Water Framework Directive and reports to EFTA Surveillance Authority (2023). The norwegian government needs now to respond to EU to these raised issues.
Netherlands	Hollande Luchte	Missing scenario	Hollandse Luchten started as a pilot in 2018 and has developed into a citizen measurement network with measurement groups at various locations in North Holland.
		Engage authorities to enforce set targets	Hollandse Luchten could develop into a tool for local authorities to address problems in the region. For example: the province wants to evaluate the official air quality network and can ask the Hollandse Luchten community
		Engage entities with environmental impact to encourage compliance to targets	Many stakeholders involved: province pays for the project, but cities and other parties, like RIVM, TNO etc.
		Take solution-driven practical action	Citizens are discussing the issues they are worried about, device a measurement plan, do the measurements and do the analysis - everything with the help of other stakeholders in the project
			Fab Lab: Waag Amsterdam provided sensor technology, data visualization, but also mediation and support in bringing the reults to the media
Map- note the measurement questions on the map https://hollandse-luchten.org/kaart/ _the data feeds also into samenmeten.rivm.nl			
Bolivia	Deforestation and fire prevention in Bolivia	Engage entities with environmental impact to encourage compliance to targets	Facilitate collaboration among like minded indigenous organisations and NGOs - agendas of common concern
			Engage with UNCHR to showcase the threats faced by the communities
			Provide input on the militarization of indigenous land
		Invited to provide input in new env. legislation	
	Engage authorities to enforce set targets	Establish direct ways of collaborating with public authorities	
		Easy and safe ways of making authorities aware of deforestation / fire	
Organisation development and institutional strengthening of indigenous territorial governance - enforcement of own rules, monitoring			

			Invite local rangers to participate in patrols and community monitoring and enforce the law
			Local authorities organized few patrols (based on community data) after pressure from US embassy
		Engage authorities to change or create policy/regulation (supra or national level)	Participating in new policy or law processes
		Engage with media to generate attention about the topic	Strategic actions to engage media at local level and beyond - radio, news media, some
			Feed our data collection to media in order to build awareness for the problem
			Making reports and communication outputs with the results of the monitoring and feeding them in National media. BANG! The issue has entered the weekly national media agenda.
		(radical) Activist action	Facilitate data forest monitoring data collection.
		Encourage responsible authority/policy maker to reassess the monitoring framework	Communicate our findings with Ministry of Environment and encourage them to provide comments and take action
Take legal action (or require authorities to do so)	Insist that authorities take action - continued call for action, ally up with other organisations		
Ireland	CoastWatch	Engage authorities to enforce set targets	SUP Directive - Banned Items Cluster of actions including meetings with authorities, resulting in enforcement letters being sent. International Workshop
		Celebrate! a step to improvement	Nitrates & Biodiversity Bannow Bay, engaged with Teagasc, IFA, NPWS, LAWPRO & local farmers & citizens
		Take solution-driven practical action	Water Quality Farmers EIP/ NbS to stop pollution/ other landowners & community Public events - farmers seen more positively as good impact & others inspired by NbS
Norway	Air Pollution in Norway	(not really radical) Activist action	One positive outcome came from a follow up action: print of all the letters sent throughout the years and showing it (it was picked up by the media)
			The example: Kristiansand: CSI (neighbourhood association) organised an email campaign to various stakeholders (industry, public authorities,

			research institute) for every time that they identified a breach of air pollution rules
			CSI also take screenshot of air pollution values, photos of fumes
		Picked up by media to generate attention about the topic	Results: no-follow up, letters go directly to the bin, receivers of letters feel like it's email bomb
			Answers they receive from industry is that it was unforeseen
Portugal	Biblitzes in Portugal	Engage authorities to enforce set targets	Initiated by an NGO (Biodiversity4All) that holds a CS platform in Portugal and have gathered the attention from local authorities that now want to promote more bioblitzes to collect data to be used in their reports, to engage their own personnel and to engage citizens.
		Engage with media to generate attention about the topic	Several news have been produced on bioblitzes and on the effects that this type of action can have at several levels.
Norway	Prevent marine plastic litter	Engage with media to generate attention about the topic	#likefinsomfør is a social media campaign organised by the CSI old Norge Rent's national awareness-raising work against littering.
			Contact media to address litter issues connected to specific stakeholders (e.g. ENGOs have addressed littering from farming).
		Engage entities with environmental impact to encourage compliance to targets	The CSI HNR has established and run and collaborate around (so beyond the data per se), with some basic funding from the authorities, the rydde.no portal and knowledge base on litter data
			Engage key stakeholders in understanding their pollution problem and solutions (e.g. researchers , engaged waste management workers and keep Norway Beautiful has engaged the fishing and aquaculture industry and the construction industry in addressing their plastic pollution problem through a number of initiatives(
			Report littering to authorities (e.g. municipalities that are responsible authority for littering)
		Take solution-driven practical action	Make decision makers aware of solutions (eg seagull safe bins)
Engage producers in re-thinking product/service design (e.g. Keep Norway Beautiful has a program that addresses producers and service providers in design to prevent pollution)			
Arrange clean-up days (national dedicated days, local arrangements)			

			Provide feedback to citizen scientists on what the data they collect is used for (Keep Norway Beautiful produces annual reports)
Italy	Zero Pollution	Engage with media to generate attention about the topic	Italian case study also engages with media to generate attention (MICS project newspaper reports)
Sierra Leone		Engage entities with environmental impact and engaging authorities to enforce set targets	In Sierra Leone, citizens engage authorities to create policy regulation (by providing the data which relates to SDG632) They also encourage the responsible authority to reassess the monitoring framework
Denmark	Biodiversity	Take solution-driven practical action	Collection of dead seabirds, being sent to authorities to investigate cause of death / amount of plastic in stomach
			DN beach cleans and removal of invasive species
			Keep Denmark Tidy beach cleans
			Biodiversity (species) ambassadors https://deungebio.dk/

Annex II

Tool Title
Activist Handbook - Campaigning guides for activists
Description
The Activist Handbook is a guide for grassroots activists committed to environmental protection through non-violent direct action. Covering essential strategies, techniques, and principles, the handbook empowers individuals and communities to take action against ecological destruction. It offers practical advice on organizing campaigns, planning protests, and ensuring safety, while emphasizing values such as collaboration, inclusivity, and sustainability. Designed for beginners and experienced activists alike, the manual serves as both a resource and an inspiration, encouraging creative, ethical, and impactful resistance.
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Activist Handbook - Campaigning guides for activists

Tool Title
Building community through social media
Description
Social media platforms are essential tools for mobilizing activists, despite challenges like censorship and shadow bans. Popular platforms like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok can be leveraged to promote causes, engage supporters, and organize solution-driven practical actions. Citizen and communities can use platforms to amplify messages and campaigns, fostering meaningful relationships, and mobilize large audiences. Building authentic personal accounts helps create a core group of engaged supporters, leading to insightful conversations, resource sharing, and real-world impact.
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Using Facebook Groups for organizing by Blueprints for Change• Social media for change by The Good Lobby• Social Media Activism: A guide to online change making by Jessie Mawson

Tool Title
CiviCRM tool for building, engaging and organizing constituents
Description
<p>CiviCRM is an open-source, web-based Constituent Relationship Management (CRM) platform tailored for nonprofit organizations, advocacy groups, and mission-driven entities. It provides a comprehensive suite of tools to help organizations manage their relationships and interactions with constituents, donors, members, and volunteers. With features for donor and membership management, event planning, email marketing, case tracking, and detailed reporting, CiviCRM supports efficient operations and enhances engagement efforts. Designed to integrate seamlessly with popular content management systems, it serves as a flexible and cost-effective solution. Its open-source nature allows for extensive customization and community-driven development, making it an ideal choice for organizations seeking adaptable CRM solutions to advance their missions.</p>
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CiviCRM tool

Tool Title
Collection of advocacy platforms
Description
<p>Advocacy platforms provide communities with powerful tools to mobilize support, engage policymakers, and enforce environmental accountability. These platforms enable individuals and groups to create and promote petitions, amplifying their causes and gaining public and institutional attention. They empower organizations to engage and mobilize supporters through targeted actions like sending emails, making calls, or organizing events, fostering grassroots movements with measurable impacts. Additionally, they help communities and organizations organize and manage their supporters, communicate effectively, and raise funds for advocacy campaigns. Together, these tools enable citizens to coordinate campaigns, report non-compliant behaviors, and demand policy changes through petitions, public protests, and structured forums such as town hall meetings and public hearings.</p>
Link to the resource

- [Change.org](#) to create and promote petitions
- [Impactive.io](#) to help organizations engage and mobilize their supporters through targeted actions
- [NationBuilder](#) to organize and manage supporters, communicate with them, and raise funds

Tool Title
Collection of tools for effective communication in campaigns
Description
A compilation of tools designed to enhance communication in campaigns for activists and community leaders with practical resources to effectively convey their messages and drive impact. These tools offer guides and templates to reshape narratives, build public support through compelling personal stories, and craft purpose-driven content tailored for social media. They also include practical strategies for creating shareable content and leveraging community-focused storytelling to inspire action. Additionally, resources on engaging with news media equip campaigners with the skills needed to secure coverage and amplify their reach.
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Campaign Communications Course, by Global Grassroots Support Network • How to Change the Narrative: Guides, Worksheets and Templates • How to Build Public Support With Personal Stories, by Mobilisation Lab • 4 Magic Steps to Creating Shareable, Purpose-driven Social Media Content, by Mobilisation Lab • How to Change the Story on Social Media: ACF Community Toolkit, by Australian Conservation Foundation • Learn how to get covered by news media, by Activist Handbook

Tool Title
Community rights Do-It-Yourself Guide to lawmaking
Description
<p>The Community Rights DIY Guide to Lawmaking provides practical guidance and strategic insights for implementing health, safety, and welfare solutions tailored to the unique challenges of your community. Community Rights lawmaking builds upon state and federal protections for civil rights and liberties, enabling local governments to democratically enhance those protections. The guide also addresses the barriers posed by state and federal regulations that often restrict the rightful powers of local governance.</p>
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community rights Do-It-Yourself Guide to lawmaking

Tool Title
Comunitas Awards
Description
<p>The Communitas Awards is an international initiative that recognizes individuals, businesses, and organizations for their outstanding contributions to community service and social responsibility. The awards highlight efforts to combat challenges like poverty, illiteracy, pollution, and sustainability, celebrating those who foster positive community change. It also recognizes companies integrating ethics and sustainability into their business practices, as well as those promoting corporate social responsibility in innovative ways</p>
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comunitas Awards

Tool Title
Earth First! Direct Act Manual
Description
The Earth First! Direct Act Manual is almost 300 pages of diagrams, descriptions of techniques and a comprehensive overview of the role direct action plays in resistance—from planning an action, doing a soft blockade, putting up a treesit or executing a lockdown; to legal and prisoner support, direct action trainings, fun political pranks, and more. The DAM has been compiled and updated by frontline activists from around the US to help spread the knowledge and get these skills farther out in the world.
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Earth First! Direct Act Manual

Tool Title
EjAtlas - Global Atlas of Environmental Justice
Description
The Global Environmental Justice Atlas documents and catalogues social conflicts around environmental issues. It is an online interactive platform coordinated and managed by a team of researchers and activists. The content and data are the result of the work of hundreds of collaborators across the world who tell their own stories of resistance or write about what they witness. As a tool for education, networking, and advocacy, it serves strategists, activist organizers, scholars, and educators, while also empowering citizens to uncover and understand the often-overlooked environmental conflicts happening around the world.
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EjAtlas - Global Atlas of Environmental Justice

Tool Title
Empowering activist action through mailing lists
Description
Mailing lists enable rapid communication with large groups, providing updates, meeting reminders, or project news efficiently. They can also serve as a platform for idea-sharing and collaboration, fostering discussions on compliance strategies or advocacy approaches. Mailing lists encourage community engagement by organizing support initiatives, such as carpools for events or collective advocacy efforts, and also offer opportunities for fundraising and gauging subscriber interests.
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating Newsletters by Community Tool Box • Using Email Lists by Community Tool Box

Tool Title
ENPE database for environmental case law and related documents
Description
<p>The ENPE database supports the network of environmental public prosecutors across the EU by offering access to relevant criminal case law and related documents from various Member States. Currently, it focuses on three key areas of environmental law prioritized by ENPE: Air Pollution, (Transfrontier Shipments of) Waste, and Wildlife. Initially developed as part of the European Network for Implementation of Environmental Law (IMPEL - www.impel.eu), the database serves as a valuable tool for enhancing collaboration and knowledge-sharing among prosecutors tackling environmental crime. The ENPE database provides case details and judicial penalties for environmental crimes across Europe to support the ENPE network of prosecutors.</p> <p><i>As the database is primarily designed to support the ENPE network of prosecutors, access is restricted and requires authorization from ENPE.</i></p>
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Prosecutors EU

Tool Title
Environmental Compliance Handbook
Description
<p>The Environmental Compliance Handbook simplifies complex environmental laws and regulations, providing clear guidance for understanding and adhering to them. Organized into four volumes (Air, Water, Land, and Sustainability) it offers the latest regulatory updates, real-life examples, and actionable recommendations for compliance. The handbook covers emerging areas of regulation, including climate change impacts, and provides global perspectives, making it invaluable for organizations with international operations. With practical insights into preparing compliance reports and navigating new regulatory challenges, this resource is essential for industry professionals, institutions, and anyone seeking to align their practices with environmental protection and sustainability standards.</p>
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Compliance Handbook

Tool Title
EU4Environment Course on Compliance
Description
<p>This training, part of the EU4Environment: Green Economy Programme, offers three 1-hour modules showcasing EU best practices in environmental compliance assurance. Designed for Environmental Ministries and Regulators, it provides tools to promote, monitor, and enforce compliance with environmental regulations. Module 1 covers legislation, organizational design, and permitting; Module 2 focuses on compliance monitoring, including inspections and remote techniques; and Module 3 explores compliance promotion and enforcement.</p>
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU4Environment Course on Compliance

Tool Title
Leveraging chat apps for coordinated environmental action
Description
<p>Chat applications such as WhatsApp, Signal, Telegram, and others serve as effective tools for promoting practical and solution-driven actions. These platforms facilitate broad engagement by enabling secure communication, group coordination, and the dissemination of diverse content formats, including documents, videos, and real-time updates. Their widespread accessibility, low data requirements, and user-friendly interfaces make them particularly effective in low-resource settings. By supporting direct, two-way communication, chat applications allow organizations to foster trust, mobilize networks, and efficiently coordinate activities. These features position chat applications as critical tools for driving impactful, community-centered environmental initiatives.</p>
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keybase • WhatsApp (WhatsApp uses for campaign by Blueprint for change) • Facebook Groups (Using Facebook groups for campaign by Blueprint for change)

Tool Title
Massive Open Online Course: Expanding training programs at large scale
Description
<p>MOOC stands for Massive Open Online Course. It is an online learning platform designed to provide free or low-cost education to a large audience. MOOCs are typically offered by universities, organizations, or institutions and cover a wide range of topics, often with flexible access and schedules. Platforms like Coursera, edX, Udemy, and FutureLearn host MOOCs, often featuring video lectures, quizzes, peer interactions, and certification options. MOOCs can be powerful tools for large-scale training in environmental protection to citizens and communities by offering accessible, engaging, and practical content on topics like conservation, co-creation practices, and environmental law.</p>
Link to the resource

- [Coursera](#)
- [edX](#)
- [FutureLearn](#)
- [Udemy](#)
- [LinkedIn Learning](#)

Tool Title
NetRegs - Environmental compliance & best practice guidance for small and medium-sized businesses
Description
NetRegs is a free online resource that provides environmental guidance for small and medium-sized businesses in Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland. Created through a partnership between the Northern Ireland Environment Agency (NIEA) in Northern Ireland and the Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA), it provides sector-specific advice to help businesses comply with environmental laws and adopt sustainable practices. NetRegs features clear explanations of regulations, practical tools, templates, and tips for reducing environmental impact. With regular updates on legal changes and industry best practices, NetRegs empowers businesses to enhance their sustainability while staying compliant, ensuring a positive contribution to environmental protection.
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.netregs.org.uk/

Tool Title
Online community for knowledge exchange
Description
Online community platforms provide dynamic spaces for knowledge exchange, collaboration, and collective action, enabling individuals from diverse backgrounds to connect and share resources. Through dedicated channels, participants can discuss topics of interest, co-develop solutions to environmental challenges, and organize local and global initiatives. Features like real-time messaging, file sharing, and video conferencing foster inclusive participation, empowering citizens to take ownership of conservation efforts. By providing accessible spaces for dialogue, sharing best practices, and hosting virtual

workshops or campaigns, these platforms help build a collective sense of responsibility toward environmental challenges. They enable geographically dispersed participants to co-create solutions, organize grassroots actions, and amplify advocacy efforts.

Link to the resource

- [Discord](#)
- [Slack](#)

Tool Title

Open Collective Platform

Description

Open Collective is a platform designed to support community-driven projects through transparent fundraising, expense management, and governance. It allows groups to raise funds, manage expenses, and ensure financial transparency, giving stakeholders visibility into how money is spent. The platform promotes collaboration, where contributors can engage in decision-making and work together on open-source, social impact, and creative initiatives. Key features include real-time financial tracking, collective fundraising, and community governance. Open Collective is ideal for open-source projects, social causes, and creative endeavours, enabling efficient, transparent management of community-led efforts.

Link to the resource

- [Open Collective Platform](#)

Tool Title

Open repository for discovering Fab Labs worldwide

Description

FabLabs.io is an open, collaborative platform that connects users to a global network of spaces with adapted infrastructure for digital fabrication. Through FabLabs.io, users can find detailed information about these spaces, their locations, available equipment, and membership options. The platform highlights these hubs

as dynamic environments for collaboration, innovation, and knowledge exchange, where individuals, startups, researchers, and communities can co-create, experiment, and refine prototypes. FabLabs.io also facilitates access to global events, workshops, and community-driven initiatives, making it an essential tool for anyone looking to develop ideas, learn new skills, or engage in hands-on, creative problem-solving.

Link to the resource

- <https://www.fablabs.io/>

Tool Title

Open source repositories to develop products for materials recycling

Description

Open-source repositories enabled the co-development and sharing of files and designs to create machinery for different types of products, democratizing access to tools for circular economy practices. These open-source resources encourage innovation, collaboration, and skill-sharing, enabling individuals and organizations to address, for example, waste management challenges. Users can download designs to build products themselves or connect with local makers listed on the platforms to collaborate.

Link to the resource

- [Precious Plastic](#)
- [Opendesk](#)

Tool Title

Paradise Now! A climate justice Handbook for Young People

Description

Paradise Now! A Handbook for Climate Justice is a resource designed for use by young people, climate activists, and educators. It offers a diverse collection of materials, including worksheets, activities, comic strips, artworks, manifestos, oral histories, discussions, social media content, and other creative experiments in climate justice activism. The handbook aims to inspire imagination and foster solidarity, both essential for transforming societies and individuals in response to the climate crisis.

Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Paradise Now!

Tool Title
Project management tools for organizing practical action
Description
<p>Project management tools provide a structured approach to planning, coordinating, and executing actions that tackle environmental challenges. They enable organizers to break down complex issues into manageable tasks, assign responsibilities, and track progress efficiently. Features such as timeline creation, task prioritization, collaboration spaces, and resource allocation ensure that all team members stay aligned with the movement's goals. These tools foster communication, allowing users to share updates, collaborate on ideas, and mobilize communities for collective action.</p>
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trello • Microsoft To Do • Asana

Tool Title
Public Participation Guide: Internet Resources on Public Participation
Description
<p>The EPA's Public Participation Guide is a resource designed to assist government agencies in fostering meaningful public engagement in environmental decision-making. It provides practical tools tailored to different aspects of public participation, including techniques to inform the public, ensuring stakeholders have the information they need to understand the project and decision-making process. It also includes tools to generate and obtain input and offers tools for consensus building and agreement-seeking, which facilitate collaboration among diverse stakeholders, fostering shared learning and joint decision-making. With its emphasis on best practices, trust-building, and effective program design, the guide supports agencies in creating inclusive and impactful public participation</p>

programs that align with principles of good governance and environmental responsibility.

Link to the resource

- [Public Participation Guide](#)

Tool Title

SISCODE Toolkit: A Toolbox for Co-Creation Journeys

Description

The SISCODE Toolbox aims to facilitate the design and implementation of co-creation journeys, focussing on better understanding and prioritisation of the particularities of each context. The selection of tools and toolkits intend to support the development of design-based processes from the problem analysis to the ideation of a solution, the development of a prototype and its experimentation in a real-world context. The resource includes a set of canvases and basic instructions for their use for 4 phases of co-creation: Analyse the Context, Reframe the Problem, Envision Alternatives, and Prototype and Experiment.

Link to the resource

- [SISCODE Toolbox](#)

Tool Title

The United Nations Environment Programme's (UNEP) Guidelines for Compliance

Description

The United Nations Environment Programme's (UNEP) Guidelines for Compliance provide a framework to support governments, international organizations, NGOs, the private sector, and other stakeholders in enhancing adherence to multilateral environmental agreements (MEAs). These guidelines are relevant to current and future MEAs and address a wide range of environmental challenges, including global environmental protection, hazardous substance management, pollution prevention, desertification, biodiversity conservation, and human health. They are designed to facilitate the integration of

compliance measures during the negotiation and design of MEAs and guide their implementation after entry into force. By promoting effective compliance strategies, national laws and policies, and fostering subregional, regional, and international cooperation, the guidelines aim to strengthen the implementation and effectiveness of MEAs for sustainable environmental governance.

Link to the resource

- [The United Nations Environment Programme's \(UNEP\) Guidelines for Compliance](#)

Tool Title

Whistleblowing Toolkit

Description

Protect's Environmental Whistleblowing Toolkit is a guide designed to help individuals safely and effectively raise environmental concerns. Developed in collaboration with trade unions, legal experts, NGOs, and journalists, the toolkit provides practical and legal advice tailored to whistleblowing in workplace settings. It covers key topics such as identifying what constitutes an environmental concern, practical steps for raising such concerns, and understanding your legal rights as a whistleblower. This resource empowers individuals to take action confidently while maximizing impact and ensuring personal safety.

Link to the resource

- [Whistleblowing Toolkit](#)

Tool Title
Working with creatives: Citizen Led Action Toolkit – CitiObs Toolkit
Description
<p>Working with Creatives, part of the Citizen-Led Action Toolkit by CitiObs, explores the potential of engaging creative communities, such as artists and cultural practitioner, in citizen observatories (COs). Creative culture and art communities are powerful drivers of innovation and imagination, offering fresh perspectives and unconventional solutions to local and global challenges. By involving creatives in citizen-led actions, COs can benefit from dynamic, engaging approaches that resonate with diverse audiences and inspire greater participation. This tool highlights how collaboration with local artists and creatives can enhance CO activities, helping to develop new narratives, foster emotional connections, and encourage more sustainable actions. It emphasizes the importance of leveraging artistic processes to generate impactful, transformative change, while expanding the reach and influence of citizen-led initiatives.</p>
Link to the resource
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CitiObs Toolkits

Annex III

Issue

*What is the issue/situation that is triggering the action?
What environmental degradation is being caused? In which geographical area? What behaviour or decisions are causing the degradation?*

Duty Holders

Who has responsibilities and obligations under current rules & regulations?

Compliance Situation

What is the actual situation? Are duty holders compliant with relevant rules & regulations? Could they do more?

Existing Community reactions

Are there any citizen and communities already engaged to address this issue? What type of actions/reactions have already taken place?

Why is the compliance situation happening?

*What are the attitudes and motivations of non-compliant duty holders?
Are responsibilities and obligations clear and enforceable?
Is current environmental compliance assurance effective?*

CCLA TARGET

*Based on your insights from the Issue Card:
Are you targeting duty holders directly, policy makers or
ineffective ECA actors?*

Public Authority

*Who are the public authorities (institutional actors) with a
formal role in the situation? (e.g. environmental regulator,
inspector, enforcement agency, legal system (judge,
prosecutor), legislative body (local, regional, national))*

Core CCLA stakeholders

Co-design team

*Which stakeholders will lead/contribute to the design
& deployment of the CCLA? Roles & responsibilities?*

Citizens & Communities

*Which citizens and/or groups will participate in the action? How
will they be engaged? What role(s) will they play?*

*What are the motivation(s) and emotion(s) for the
core CCLA stakeholders to act on the situation?*

Networking with External Partnerships

*With whom can you collaborate during the CCLA? Who can support you?
(Fab Labs, Living labs, Legal experts, nGOs ?)
What type of partnerships may you have to create?*

Extended CCLA network

3. CCLA GOAL CARD

SITUATE YOUR CCLA

CCLA STATEMENT

Please briefly describe the goal of your action

Interactions

What is the interaction with the target of the action and with relevant public authorities? (please tick corresponding box(es))

	Interactions with Target (tick)	Interactions with Public Authority (tick)	Interactions with Public Authority (tick)	Interactions with Public Authority (tick)
Collaborative	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Confrontational	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Outcomes

Which outputs/outcomes are you aiming for?

- Prevent non-compliance
- Diagnose non-compliance
- Respond to non-compliance
- Direct environmental outcome
- Policy improvement
- Strengthen the ECA system
- Other (please specify)

Purpose

What are the main purpose(s) of your planned action?

- Supportive**
Directed towards targets who are confused, careless or under-resourced, serves to change their behaviour by altering the knowledge and resources available to them.
- Critical**
Directed towards targets who are opportunistic, contemptuous or criminal, serves to influence their behaviours and decisions by generating social and institutional pressures.

Action Types

Situate yourself among the types of CCLAs

- Assist duty holders to encourage compliance
- Generate public pressure
- Demand changes in environmental practices
- Pro-active conservation and recovery actions
- Organise citizen patrols & watch
- Denounce violations committed with impunity
- Report non-compliance to authorities
- Take legal action
- Inhibit non-compliance via civilian interventions

4. DEFINE YOUR OWN ACTION PATHWAY

Revisit your goal card if needed

more4nature
with citizen science

PROCESS

Similar to the steps in the **Repertoire of Action Pathways**, identify the steps that you will take for the implementation of the CCLA in order to achieve the goal and purpose of your CCLA.

SKILLS AND RESOURCES

What are the required skills and resources you need to implement each step of the CCLA process?

TOOLS & PARTNERSHIPS

What tools & methods you would like to apply at each step of the CCLA process?
What partnerships would you seek? Is there expertise in other initiatives, organisations, networks that can help implement the CCLA, such as Fab Labs or Living Labs?

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5. MEASURE CCLA IMPACT CARD

DEFINE

*What impact do you want to create with your action?
What would make it a success? What specific internal or external outcomes are you aiming for?*

INTERNAL OUTCOMES

*Sense of urgency & achievement, capacity,
skills, resources, sense of collective*

EXTERNAL OUTCOMES

*Prevent non-compliance
Diagnose non-compliance
Respond to non-compliance
Direct environmental outcome
Policy improvement
Strengthen the ECA system
Other (please specify)*

Remember to check your CCLA Goal Card

MEASURE

What is the actual impact of the action(s)? What can you learn from this experience?

NEXT

*What adaptations does your strategy need, in the short or long term?
What other CCLA(s) may need to be implemented?*

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